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TITLE Evaluating the Potential of Centrifugal Microfluidic Platforms for Livestock Disease Detection in a Developing Country

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Abstract

This dissertation evaluates the market potential and barriers to implementing centrifugal Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) diagnostic technology in Paraguay's livestock sector, addressing critical gaps in point-of-care testing for developing countries by identifying the needs of the key stakeholders. A survey, conducted through a questionnaire involving 150 farmers and veterinarians, examines current diagnostic practices, barriers to the adoption of new technologies, and stakeholder concerns and preferences for diagnostic solutions. Findings reveal significant diagnostic inadequacies, with 61.3% of respondents conducting livestock health monitoring only seasonally or less frequently. Access-related barriers, including distance to laboratories and prolonged turnaround times, emerged as primary obstacles preventing regular testing. However, 95% expressed strong willingness to adopt simple, cost-effective diagnostic methods, indicating substantial market receptivity. Brucellosis, mastitis, and foot-and-mouth disease are identified as optimal targets for Point-of-Care testing and LoaD development, based on economic impact and technical compatibility with centrifugal microfluidic platforms. For market entry, large farms demonstrated early adoption potential, prioritizing proven effectiveness and peer testimonials over purely financial incentives. Implementation strategies emphasize veterinarian recommendations and training through face-to-face demonstrations, supported by the cooperative-based networks. The research demonstrates significant potential for antimicrobial stewardship. These findings provide an adaptable framework for LoaD technology deployment in developing countries, supporting global efforts to combat antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance while improving livestock health management efficiency and economic sustainability.

Resumen

Esta tesis evalúa el potencial de mercado y las barreras para implementar la tecnología diagnóstica centrífuga Laboratorio-en-un-Disco (LoaD) en el sector ganadero de Paraguay, abordando brechas críticas en las pruebas, en el punto de atención en países en desarrollo mediante la identificación de necesidades de los principales involucrados. Se aplicó un cuestionario a 150 productores y veterinarios para analizar prácticas diagnósticas actuales, obstáculos de adopción y preocupaciones y preferencias sobre soluciones de diagnósticos. Los resultados revelan deficiencias en el

monitoreo sanitario: 61.3% realiza controles de salud del ganado solo estacionalmente o con menor frecuencia. Las barreras de acceso —distancia a laboratorios y prolongados tiempos de entrega— fueron los principales impedimentos para pruebas regulares. No obstante, 95% manifestó fuerte disposición a adoptar métodos de diagnósticos simples y de bajo costo, indicando alta receptividad del mercado. Brucelosis, mastitis y fiebre aftosa fueron identificadas como óptimas para análisis en el punto de atención y tecnología LoaD. Para la entrada al mercado, establecimientos de gran escala mostraron mayor potencial de adopción temprana, priorizando eficacia comprobada y recomendaciones de pares por sobre incentivos financieros. Las estrategias de implementación destacan a los veterinarios como agentes clave, con capacitaciones presenciales y demostraciones prácticas, apoyadas por redes de Cooperativas. La investigación muestra alto potencial para fortalecer el uso responsable de antimicrobianos. Estos hallazgos ofrecen un marco adaptable para implementar LoaD en países en desarrollo, contribuyendo a combatir la resistencia antimicrobiana y a mejorar la eficiencia en la gestión sanitaria del ganado y la sostenibilidad económica del sector.

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DECLARATIONS

I declare that the material contained in this dissertation is the end result of my own work and that due acknowledgement has been given in the bibliography and references to ALL sources be they printed, electronic or personal.

And that:

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1. Introduction and Background

Livestock production is a cornerstone of the agricultural economy, and the cattle sector is a key contributor to protein supply. In recent years, the value of farmed animals worldwide has been estimated at between 1.61 trillion USD and 3.3 trillion USD, underscoring the immense economic and social impact of this industry (Ederer et al., 2023; Schrobback et al., 2023). Cattle, which include not only cows but also bulls and other bovines, represent a cornerstone in both developed and developing countries. Bellmann et al. (2004) explain the distinction between beef and dairy cattle, which influences production systems and the management challenges faced by farmers related to attributes such as their muscle and body fat.

Strydom et al. (2023, p. 3) lists the United States and Brazil as the leading beef producers. Sustainability of the cattle sector remains threatened, particularly in developing countries. Small and medium-scale farmers often operate on narrow margins and face persistent barriers to accessing efficient and timely veterinary diagnostics. These diagnostic challenges have far-reaching consequences, ranging from increased herd losses and reduced productivity to broader public health risks associated with zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance. This thesis examines the potential for Point-of-Care testing, often utilizing centrifugal microfluidic technologies and incorporating Lab-on-a-Disc tests, to transform livestock disease detection in settings where resources are limited and infrastructure is underdeveloped. This work explores whether such technologies can bridge current gaps and support more efficient, sustainable, and profitable cattle management in developing countries.

1.1. Research Environment

This section provides a brief introduction to diagnostic areas and an overview of diagnostics, including livestock-related diagnostics, with a primary focus on existing diseases, market environment, and a short estimation of market needs for livestock

in developing countries.

1.1.1. Importance of Diagnostics

Accurate and timely diagnostics play a fundamental role in animal health management. Francis (2022) highlights how important it is to obtain a result in a short time. Early detection of disease in livestock enables targeted interventions that minimize losses, reduce the spread of infection, and promote animal welfare, as shown in Kyriazakis et al. (2024). Additionally, it is estimated that improved animal health reduces environmentally harmful emissions. Railey and Marsh (2021) shows that when anaplasmosis enters a herd, it reduces body weight by 20% to 30%. Because zoonotic diseases are responsible for more than 2.7 million human deaths annually, Carter and Smith (2021) pointed out the need for growth in veterinary laboratory diagnostics. Robust diagnostic systems are essential for effective disease control strategies, decreasing reliance on routine antibiotic use, to address global challenges such as antimicrobial resistance Horvat and Kovačević (2025); Hosain et al. (2021). Understanding the diagnostic landscape and economic dynamics of diagnostic technologies is vital for guiding future innovation and adoption, and bringing them in line with market needs in developing countries.

1.1.2. Diagnostic Market

Depending on the source, there are significant differences in market sizes and forecasts. Depending on various system boundaries and other factors. The compound annual growth rate (CAGR), with the formula $CAGR = \left(\frac{V_{\text{final}}}{V_{\text{begin}}}\right)^{1/t} - 1$, which normalizes the growth by year, exhibits overall similar trends. Only by whole diagnostics Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd. (2024a) deviates sharply downwards with CAGR, and Bora (2025) by microfluidics deviates sharply upwards with CAGR.

Table 1.1 visualizes different forecasts and CAGR. The starting estimation varies often. It is assumed that it depends on other defined system boundaries. As long as the same definition is used within the same market report for the forecast, the CAGR can be applied.

Market/ Technique	Current USD Billion (Year)	Forecast USD Billion (Year)	CAGR (%)	Source
Diagnostics	286 (2024)	546 (2032)	8.4	(Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd., 2024a)
	211 (2023)	450 (2033)	7.9	(Nova One Advisor, 2025)
	210 (2023)	273 (2034)	3	(Precedence Research, 2024)
Microfluidics	31 (2024)	94 (2032)	15	(Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd., 2025)
	40 (2025)	116 (2034)	12.5	(Towards Healthcare, 2025)
	36 (2024)	41 (2025)	12.3	(Market Data Forecast, 2025)
	32 (2024)	223 (2033)	24	(Bora, 2025)
Lab-on-a-Chip	6.3 (2021)	13 (2029)	9.5	(Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd., 2022)
	6.8 (2023)	15.6 (2032)	9.7	(SNS Insider pvt ltd, 2025)
	7 (2024)	13.5 (2031)	9.7	(Extrapolate, 2025)
Point-of-Care Test- ing	41 (2024)	87 (2032)	10	(Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd., 2024c)
	41 (2023)	60 (2030)	7.5	(Wissen Research LLC, 2025)
	32 (2024)	51 (2032)	6.2	(Fortune Business Insights, 2025)
Livestock Diagnos- tics	2.3 (2023)	4.2 (2031)	7.8	(Data Bridge Market Research Private Ltd., 2024b)
	1.35 (2023)	2.56 (2031)	8.4	(Pawar and Khillari, 2024)
	1.52 (2024)	2.94 (2032)	8.6	(SkyQuest Technology Group, 2025)

Table 1.1.: Approximate data and predictions for diagnostics, POCT, and the livestock market, and LoaC and microfluidics technologies are compared (Riedel, 2025).

Diagnostics represents a substantial market with significant growth projections. The microfluidics technology is a smaller, specialized segment, but shows over proportional growth compared to the whole diagnostic market. Lab-on-a-Chip (LoaC or LoC) is a key technology in microfluidics, and is often utilized in Point-of-Care Testing (POCT). POCT outpaces the general diagnostic market growth trend. The growth in livestock diagnostics is driven by the rise in global animal protein consumption and increasing awareness of zoonotic¹ diseases.

The Origin of POC In [Manassis et al. \(2022\)](#), it is explained that initially, POC testing was primarily used in human medicine, mainly for diseases that are more prevalent in developing countries. Later, it continued with a more economical focus, for example, on zoonoses and COVID-19. It concludes that a similar observation was not visible up to 2022, when the paper was written, for animal diseases.

Used Diagnostic Categorization For a general overview and orientation, the [Figure 1.1](#) illustrates the key diagnostic categories applicable for human and animal. For this research, the comparison of traditional centralized laboratory tests with microfluidics, which is a game changer in POCT, is relevant, as underlined in [Sachdeva et al. \(2021\)](#); [Yuan et al. \(2025\)](#). In [Yang et al. \(2022b\)](#), it is mentioned that the use of microfluidics in Point-of-Care (POC) has several advantages, including integration and commercialization. Microfluidics is increasingly integrated into centralized laboratory settings as well and does not replace them ([Fibben et al., 2025](#)). To better understand the phases in diagnostics, Figure 2 in [Fibben et al. \(2025, pp. 2566-2567\)](#) provides a helpful overview of the common sense of the three phases in diagnostics: pre-analytical, analytical, and post-analytical.

¹ zoonotic: a disease which could be transmitted between animals and humans

Figure 1.1.: Overview of diagnostic modalities (Manassis et al., 2022; Miyazaki et al., 2020).

Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) empowers microfluidics by eliminating the need for external pumps and complex infrastructure, utilizing a simple motor that produces three forces to manipulate fluids. This technology is promising for resource-limited environments and settings, as explained in more depth in Chapter 2 in Section 2.4.

Point-of-Care Point-of-Care (POC) devices are known for their simplicity in the diagnostic device palette and are in the lower-cost segment (Henderson et al., 2016, p. 126). The complex risk mitigation to prevent cross-contamination from other samples, such as filters in disposable tips (DiLorenzo et al., 2001), long process protocols, and sometimes time-consuming and research-intensive wash cycles for tubes in liquid handling robotics, as introduced in Frégeau et al. (2007), are often

obsolete to using POC devices. Especially in “contamination-sensitive molecular diagnostic assays [Kong et al. \(2016, p. 335\)](#)”, it is a remarkable advantage.

Multiplexed Point-of-Care Testing (xPOCT) An additional emerging field for developing countries with low financial capabilities. It provides multiple detections of different test results that are performed simultaneously from a single sample. The terms are well-introduced in the paper by [Dincer et al. \(2017\)](#), including a glossary. In [Figure 1.2](#), an overview is provided of the low complexity and high performance of an ideal XPOCT compared to other diagnostic areas, such as the central laboratory. The author estimates that an ideal POC is less complex, especially in terms of development, but also has reduced performance due to the lack of parallelized analytics. Actual research which shows the differences between state-of-the-art (non-ideal) XPOCT or POC to central laboratory is elaborated in [Section 2.4.5](#).

Figure 1.2.: Overview of how xPOCT is related to centralized laboratory testing regarding complexity and performance, simplified figure from the paper [Dincer et al. \(2017, p. 739\)](#)

Extreme Point-of-Care Testing (EPOCT) The most significant difference between Extreme Point-of-Care testing and Point-of-Care testing is the harsher envi-

ronment and less developed infrastructure for healthcare, such as roads, as well as other factors in developing countries, as explained in [Michael et al. \(2016\)](#).

1.1.3. Overview of Livestock

By reviewing 192 peer-reviewed papers and organization-published reports [Kappes et al. \(2023\)](#) found a lack of knowledge about the global impact of animal diseases, especially in terms of revenue reduction and economic effects throughout the livestock value chain. Diseases in livestock and their impact on the local population will affect global challenges for the next decades. A resource-efficient production approach that reduces livestock losses due to disease also lowers global CO₂ emissions. Diseased cattle take longer to reach slaughter weight and therefore emit more gases, as explained in [Kyriazakis et al. \(2024\)](#). In [Kozicka et al. \(2023\)](#), the high correlation between human and cattle populations in developing countries, as well as the higher methane emissions that could be reduced by increasing efficiency in cattle management, is detailed.

Disease Detection in Animals Another use case for POC devices and testing methods is the detection of disease in animals, discussed in ([Yang et al., 2022b](#)). Especially for livestock, there is a vast potential to reduce mortality and prevent the spread of disease in cattle, cows, small ruminants (sheep and goats), and pig herds. The next three subsections follow a brief introduction to most diseases, particularly those affecting cows and cattle, an overview of the global market, and a focus on the Paraguayan market. More information about the current state, including what is done in livestock related to detection and control of animal health, and monitoring herds to prevent widespread infection, is explained in [Chapter 2](#) in [Section 2.1.1](#).

Paraguayan Market Environment Gathering data in a developing country can end up challenging for several reasons. Often development countries stays not in the economical hot spot like Europe and North America, and frequently exists a lack of organization capabilities. Data are sometimes outdated. [López \(2025\)](#) identified the corruption and the strong influence on the outcome of results, which favors the economic elites, who are also political actors, to their most significant advantage. The ranking of 149 out of 180 listed countries in the corruption index from [Transparency International \(2024\)](#) also supports this paper's statement. This circumstance often

results in ideological decisions in economic and political matters related to other members and society, rather than decisions based on rational considerations and aimed at achieving the highest level of efficiency. The author Peck (2025) mentions in the Global Beef article that 3% of landowners hold almost 90% of the farmland in Paraguay.

Paraguay Cattle Numbers According to the report by Joseph (2024), the Paraguay cattle population has been estimated at approximately 13.5 million in recent years. The price per kilogram tends to decrease even though inflation has been around 5% (FocusEconomics, 2025). The report uses the data from SENACSA, the National Service of Quality and Animal Health in Paraguay (Servicio Nacional de Calidad y Salud Animal, 2025). Over 145 thousand cattle herds are estimated by Rural Association of Paraguay (2019). The structure of farms in Paraguay, as explained by a Paraguayan expert with an Agricultural Management degree, is illustrated in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3.: Farm structures and strategies in Paraguay

Export and Size Comparison In the first half of 2025, Paraguay became the eighth top beef exporter, as reported in Martinez (2025). In South America, Paraguay is

the third-largest producer. In the [Figure 1.4](#), the total cattle per country of the four leading producers in South America are visualized. Different numbers of cattle heads, depending on the source, are available. For this visualization to illustrate the relations, the numbers from [World Population Review \(2023\)](#) are chosen.

Figure 1.4.: Total cattle herd by country in 2023. Uruguay: 11.9M (3.7%), Paraguay: 13.5M (4.3%), Argentina: 54.2M (17%), Brazil: 238M (75%)

1.2. Research Problem

Paraguay and many other developing countries have fewer resources for centralized laboratories. The landscape of Paraguay is more than 10% larger than that of Germany, but its population is around 12 times smaller. Often, the large distances to the next veterinarian or centralized laboratory ([Francis, 2022](#), Figure 2) combined with poor infrastructure conditions and a lengthy wait for a diagnosis from the laboratory ([Hobbs et al., 2021](#)) result in gaps in accessibility and efficiency. Paraguay's cattle sector, with 13.5 million head ([Joseph, 2024](#)), is the third-largest in South America and a substantial source of income for a significant portion of the country's population. Delayed disease detection results in substantial economic losses and risks for the families and communities.

Economic Constraints Small and medium-scale farmers, who represent a significant portion of Paraguay's livestock sector, face financial barriers to accessing diagnostic services. Centralized laboratory testing is time-consuming and cost-intensive. Therefore, is the livestock sector a price-sensitive market with narrow margin bandwidths (Manassis et al., 2022). Preventing disease outbreaks requires massive use of tests. The test and transport costs must be low, with a short turnaround time for results.

Technology Gap Current point-of-care testing in veterinary medicine remains underdeveloped compared to human diagnostics. Due to the smaller market size and economic margins, the interest of the bigger producers is limited (Manassis et al., 2022).

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) Concerns The overuse of antibiotics, particularly for preventive purposes in the absence of rapid diagnostics, contributes to the growing global problem of antimicrobial resistance (Horvat and Kovačević, 2025). The often-unawareness in developing countries about the correct use of antibiotics and the lack of knowledge about side effects, such as AMR, resulting from misuse and overuse, negatively influences the global health (Hosain et al., 2021). Paraguay's livestock sector requires diagnostic tools that enable targeted therapeutic interventions.

Identified Need These challenges underscore the need for accessible, cost-effective, and rapid diagnostic solutions, especially in developing countries. Lab-on-a-Disc technology presents a potential solution by offering simplified sample handling, reduced reagent requirements, and the possibility of point-of-care testing without extensive infrastructure requirements (Hobbs et al., 2021; Michael et al., 2016) A successful implementation of new technologies requires careful consideration of local contexts and the needs of farmers and veterinarians. This involves identifying and implementing frameworks adapted to Paraguay's specific conditions in the livestock sector, as well as identifying potential learnings for other developing countries.

1.3. Research Aim

This research aims to critically evaluate the potential and barriers for implementing centrifugal Lab-on-a-Disc diagnostic technologies in Paraguay's livestock management systems through a detailed understanding of market needs. It elaborates on challenges and environmental conditions in Paraguay and discusses a framework that could be generalized for developing countries.

1.4. Research Objectives

The three objectives of this study are to elaborate evidence-based recommendations for a successful strategy to implement LoAD technology in livestock cattle farms in developing countries, particularly in Paraguay, by examining market needs, cultural aspects, and environmental situations.

All objectives are timely aligned with the [Gantt chart 3.1](#) in [Section 3.5](#).

Objectives:

1. To critically evaluate current livestock diagnostic practices among farmers and veterinarians in Paraguay, identifying quantifiable gaps in current diagnostic workflows and infrastructure capacity to support efficiency Improvements.
2. To investigate and identify the drivers and barriers for adoption of LoAD technology.
3. Develop an implementation framework to provide recommendations for stakeholders on optimizing the deployment of diagnostic technology in developing countries.

1.5. Research Questions

The three primary research areas, with allocated questions in this study, aim to critically evaluate how LoAD can address diagnostic needs and improve livestock health management in developing countries, particularly in Paraguay.

Market and Technology Assessment

- RQ1** What are the current livestock diagnostic practices, gaps, and needs in Paraguay's farming?
- RQ2** What specific livestock diseases would benefit most from POC, and is LoaD a potential technology option?

Adoption Barriers and Enablers

- RQ3** Which stakeholder groups show the highest potential for early adoption?
- RQ4** How are adoption decisions influenced by cultural factors, trust in technology, and information?

Implementation Framework

- RQ5** What business models and pricing strategies would make LoaD technology economically viable for farmers?
- RQ6** What training, support, and infrastructure requirements are necessary for successful implementation?

1.6. Importance of Research

This study is valuable because, as mentioned in the beginning of [Chapter 1](#), there is a knowledge gap regarding the prevalence and extent of animal diseases. In addition to the reduction of animal welfare posed by these diseases, the well-being of farmers and their families, who directly depend on the yields of their animals, is affected. A resource-efficient production approach that reduces livestock losses due to disease also lowers global CO₂ emissions. Diseased cattle take longer to reach slaughter weight and therefore emit more gases as, explained in [Kyriazakis et al. \(2024\)](#).

Another relevant aspect is the containment of the global threat posed by antimicrobial resistance. This growing problem can only be addressed through a more targeted and less excessive use of antibiotics. To achieve this, farmers need access to cost-effective testing methods. Such tests would reduce the preventive or inappropriate use of antibiotics. Since antibiotics are often inexpensive and readily available, it's crucial to determine at what testing cost a real added value and broad

acceptance among farmers can be achieved.

Ultimately, both the farmer and the veterinary doctor benefit from decreased costs and increased efficiency. Farmers are reducing their risk of losing livestock due to disease. It can support the One Health approach, as explained in [Section 2.1.1](#), for reducing antimicrobial resistance, thereby improving human health and enhancing overall well-being.

2. Current State of Research

This chapter provides an overview of the current research landscape relevant to livestock diagnostics. Beginning to give insights and understanding of the market needs and requirements by understanding diseases and problems that livestock face. Continue by comparing the livestock environment in Paraguay with that of other South American countries, continuing to demonstrate the applications of LoAD techniques in the diagnostics field. POC and LoAD in livestock, highlighting its capabilities, limitations, and its current role in livestock health management. Continuing by providing a LoAD Benefits, Risk, Mitigation Overview, and at the end a synthesis of how existing research addresses the study's research questions.

2.1. Research Overview Livestock Disease and Antimicrobial Resistance

This section presents the research findings on diseases in livestock. It highlights what antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic resistance (AR) are and how they affect global well-being. Antibiotic resistance specifically addresses bacteria that become resistant to antibiotics.

Gastrointestinal Nematodes (GIN) represent one of the most significant challenging diseases in livestock production, with the combined economic impact in Brazil and the United States alone reaching 15.6 USD Billion, as documented in table 2 by [Strydom et al. \(2023, p. 3\)](#).

External Parasites like the “tropical cattle tick, or cattle fever tick (*Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) microplus*)”([Strydom et al., 2023, p. 2](#)), and many more are dominant and cost-intensive, too. Only in Brazil, a calculated amount of 3.24 billion USD

(Strydom et al., 2023, p. 3) is attributed to these. Foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) represents one of the most economically significant diseases, affecting cattle, the primary focus of this thesis, as well as pigs, sheep, and goats. The earliest detection is crucial for preventing the spread and mitigating the negative economic impact, as shown in Yang et al. (2022a). Strategies such as virus isolation, monitoring programs, and vaccination strategies, where accurate detection of the distinct FMD variation is crucial to prevent an outbreak and recommend the best vaccine (Yang et al., 2022a, p. 6). By implementing these steps, significant positive results are shown, as discussed in Rivera et al. (2023, pp. 10-11).

Brucellosis causes economic losses in livestock and can infect other species like wildlife and some variants in humans too, explained in Díaz Aparicio (2013).

From Bovine Viral Diarrhea is Bovine Viral Diarrhea Virus (BVDV), the main microorganism, which produces a significant economic loss and is common in cattle, as discussed in Su et al. (2023, p. 2).

Several Additional Diseases for cattle exist, as well as diseases for other livestock, like Newcastle Disease for the poultry industry or swine Fever for pig populations.

Targeted Antibiotic Use in Livestock Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) is an enzyme generated by some bacteria, which causes them to become resistant (for Public Health et al., 2019) to a few or all antibiotics, explained in Bradford (2001, p. 933). Dincer (2016, p. 3) mentions the extensive use in livestock as a main driver for multi-resistant bacteria by referencing (Weber et al., 2004). In Tamma and Mathers (2021), it is noted that morbidity and mortality increase due to ESBL significantly, and mortality is declared to be up to 30% (Sianipar et al., 2019). As ESBL can be transferred from animal to human (Tamma and Mathers, 2021), Horvat and Kovačević (2025) mentions that antibiotics are overused in both therapy and prevention for humans and animals, which increases antibiotics resistance. The overuse of livestock to accelerate growth and prevent disease issues is identified as a key factor and primary artificial driver. It cites Cassini et al. (2019), which estimated over 33 thousand deaths in 2015 in the European Union. Walsh et al. (2023) forecasts globally over 10 million annual deaths by 2050 because of drug-resistant

infections, if no action is taken. They report an estimation of 4.95 million deaths globally in 2019 by citing the final report from O'Neill (2016).

2.1.1. Strategies to Combat Antimicrobial Resistance

Antibiotic susceptibility testing (AST) using microfluidic solutions helps determine the effectiveness of antibiotics against a specific bacterium, as explained in Postek et al. (2022). The implementation in livestock, especially for cattle, has enormous potential.

Campaigns to Sensitize and Tackle Antimicrobial and Antibiotic Resistance: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2025) is a science-based organization, which aims to protect the public's health, in their campaign, they inform and guide farmers, who often communicate with their veterinarian, asking for advice to prevent antimicrobial resistance, follow the instructions related to the duration of medication for the animals, and more. Another example is HealthforAnimals aisbl (2025), which shows improvements, as evidenced by data from the largest animal health organization. The data indicate that, from 2015 to 2022, vaccination in global livestock increased, while antibiotic sales decreased. Meanwhile, sales of antibiotics for humans increased, which is why they argue that not only animals but also humans require fewer antibiotics. To conclude, these goals are only reachable with a one-health approach. The authors of World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) (2025) emphasize the one health approach because humans share the same space and pathogens with animals. The research by Pandey et al. (2024, p. 272) also highlights the approach with a one health framework, which is mentioned as a paradigm part of global efforts against antibiotic resistance, as cited by World Health Organization (WHO) (2015).

2.2. Comparing Livestock Environment between Paraguay and Other South American Countries

In this section, a comparison is made between Paraguay and other countries in South America, particularly Argentina, Brazil, and Uruguay, which are all significant exporters of agricultural products, particularly meat produced from their extensive

cattle herds. This comparison is necessary to develop an applicable framework in [Chapter 5](#) that can be adapted to apply the findings in Paraguay to other developing countries, particularly in South America. This framework will support a market entering the LoAD technology in livestock, particularly in the cattle sector, to reduce costs, mitigate disease outbreaks, and enhance animal and human well-being.

Market Prices in a Competitive Environment In the weekly report [Agromeat \(2025\)](#), live cattle prices are monitored like in [Table 2.1](#).

Country	Price per Kg meat $\frac{USD}{kg}$
Paraguay	3.75
Uruguay	4.6
Argentina	4.6
Brazil	3.75

Table 2.1.: Price per kg of meat of the four largest South American meat producers

In the weekly report, the currency impacts and correlation between tropical and more moderate temperature zones are explained as the reason for the price difference. The correlation between tropical and more moderate temperature zones is not convincing, as the price is normalized per weight, and the argument according to [Ramirez Pastore and West \(2019\)](#) is more reasonable. They attribute the lower prices for Paraguayan meat to a lack of quality control and the absence of an industry association that represents the entire Paraguayan market. Meat quality standards are strongly recommended. They admire the implemented national traceability system. At the same time, they criticize that traceability is insufficient to increase brand value without a centralized controlling authority and adequate training.

Veterinarian Density in Livestock A more extensive research effort to gather the number of veterinarians involved in livestock, particularly cattle, was not successful. The only comparable numbers are from a homepage for education and training in the 1990s ([Smith and Hunter, XXXX](#), Table 5), based on data from the 1980s, which reports the following Cattle/Veterinarian Ratios in [Table 2.2](#).

Country	Cattle/Veterinarian Ratios
Paraguay	7637
Uruguay	6632
Argentina	5955
Brazil	5507

Table 2.2.: Cattle/Veterinarian Ratios of the four largest South American meat producers

2.3. Automated Test Laboratories in Livestock

Automated test laboratories benefit from their extensive experience in the market, utilizing standardized protocols and procedures. In [Carter and Smith \(2021\)](#), the need for growth in veterinary laboratory diagnostics is addressed simply because zoonotic diseases are responsible for more than 2.7 million human deaths yearly. In [International Labmate Limited \(2010\)](#), the Landeslabor Berlin-Brandenburg has a test capacity of approximately 7 thousand samples per day, utilizing ELISA assays to monitor cattle diseases and improve both human and animal health. The [Michigan State University Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory \(2025\)](#) performs around 1 million tests for more than 300 thousand animals, not only for livestock but also for zoo and exotic animals.

Importance of Turnaround Time In the paper by [Francis \(2022, pp. 220-221\)](#), which reported a study in the Sub-Saharan, the outcome revealed that the dominant challenges to submitting samples were related to the distance to the laboratory ([Francis, 2022, Figure 2](#)). The findings by [Hobbs et al. \(2021\)](#), the long distances, poor road conditions, not enough elaborated laboratories, and the long delays between taking the sample from the animal to getting the return diagnosis from the laboratory, often take days up to weeks, speak for POC systems. It concludes that these long turnaround times support the spread of new diseases.

To detect and prevent zoonotic outbreaks, access to a veterinarian is crucial, as [Crisuolo et al. \(2025\)](#) mentions a significant lack. [Velayudhan and Naikare \(2022\)](#) also highlights the increasing market need. It is clear that a further step is to

develop test methods to overcome the distance to the automated laboratories. That is an argument for POC testing with easy handling for users, ideally directly by farmers who could share a device in cooperatives and receive help interpreting the results through mobile applications with a robust algorithm in the background. The identified driver, identified risks or barriers, and [Table 2.3](#) presents proposed mitigation.

Dimension	Driver	Risks or Barriers	Mitigation/Enabler
Speed	Outbreak and spread of diseases (Criscuolo et al., 2025)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long turnaround time for central lab results (Francis, 2022) • Laboratory management and throughput bottlenecks (Hobbs et al., 2021) 	Introduce POC with LoaD testing for on-site testing with in-place decisions
Accessibility	Veterinarians and labs are often far from farms (Francis, 2022)	Distance, poor transport, lack of vets slows sample submission (Hobbs et al., 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop POC tests for cattle • Mobile testing support
Cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce herd losses (Railey and Marsh, 2021), Sections 2.6 • Lower disease spread (Carter and Smith, 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher test costs (Chin et al., 2012), Sections 2.4.4 • Device upfront investment (Mishra et al., 2023), Sections 2.4.3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device sharing by existing elaborate cooperatives. • Device payment through test costs.
User Adoption	Ease of use for farmers, paraprofessionals like veterinarians (Velayudhan and Naikare, 2022, p. 7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill gap (Railey and Marsh, 2021), Sections 2.6 • Test misinterpretation (Manassis et al., 2022, pp. 25-26), Sections 2.4.4 • Device misuse (Manassis et al., 2022, pp. 25-26), Sections 2.4.4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing training with field repetitions for veterinarians and farmers • Support with software and mobile devices • Hotline support

Table 2.3.: Summary of drivers, key risks or barriers, and practical solutions for mitigation

2.4. Lab-on-a-Chip and Lab-on-a-Disc Technology

The next two sections explore how Lab-on-a-Chip and Lab-on-a-Disc technologies work and their achievements over the last few decades.

2.4.1. Lab-on-a-Chip

Lab-on-a-Chip, which processes the liquid handling and analysis below a millimeter, reduces the amount of the volume of needed reagent, resulting in lower costs for each test [Henderson et al. \(2016\)](#). Many of the following benefits are described in ([Yang et al., 2022b](#), p. 3). The technology eliminates human interactions, resulting in less labour dependency, lower qualification level, and lower training effort. It reduces reaction time, which improves the availability of results sooner, and processing time is a crucial factor in testing costs.

The Lab-on-a-Chip, as described in the paper by [Du et al. \(2025\)](#) and referred to as a microfluidic Chip, is a technology that enables the automation of many processes by combining it with centrifugal microfluidics.

2.4.2. Lab-on-a-Disc

LoaD is a significant technology in microfluidics, as well as in Point-of-Care testing. It needs no external actuators, mentioned in [Henderson et al. \(2016, p. 116\)](#), like pumps implemented using different techniques, such as plungers or dilutors, which are mostly combined with actuators in three dimensions to process liquid handling, including moving, separating, or mixing liquids. In the LoaD technology, the fluid is driven by the principle of three different forces: Centrifugal, Euler, and Coriolis forces. This is achieved by rotating and accelerating the disc at specific rotation frequencies and accelerations. The figure [2.1](#) illustrates the physical dependencies. At constant speed and acceleration, the Centrifugal force, rotation direction independent, acts from the center radially outward. It is the main driver for fluid transport, and specific fluidic operations, concepts, and calculations are shown in [Ducrée \(2021a\)](#); [Miyazaki et al. \(2020\)](#); [Nolte \(2009\)](#).

Figure 2.1.: The directions of the different forces acting. The figure is extended from [Henderson et al. \(2016, p. 117\)](#)

An additional enabler from LoAD to simplify the process is that sample loading can be done with simple manual injection, as explained in [Henderson et al. \(2021, p. 2\)](#), for example, using a pipette.

2.4.3. LoAD Techniques Successes

[Miyazaki et al. \(2020\)](#) shows that many standard protocols like loop mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), polymerase chain reaction (PCR), enzyme-linked immuno-sorbent assay (ELISA) ([Mishra et al., 2018](#); [Thiha and Ibrahim, 2015](#)), as well as immunoreactions-based fluorescence-linked immuno-sorbent assay (FLISA) ([Nwankire et al., 2013a,0](#)) is implemented with LoAD by referencing to a plethora of papers which showing that it works

- for bacteria

- LAMP (Loo et al., 2017; Sayad et al., 2018; Seo et al., 2017)
- PCR (Amasia et al., 2012; Czilwik et al., 2015)
- for virus
 - LAMP (Chang et al., 2015; Jung et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2018)
 - PCR (Li et al., 2019; Miao et al., 2015; Stumpf et al., 2016)]

LoaD Benefits LoaD platforms are simple to use, reduce user training, and are in a low-cost range (Miyazaki et al., 2020, pp. 7-9). A whole blood ELISA application, including separation, incubation with antigen- or antibody-coated microbeads, washing, and more, which typically takes more than 2 hours in central laboratories, is demonstrated in the paper by Lee et al. (2009) to be completed in under 30 minutes. In Mishra et al. (2023) new improvements are showcased, including digital impulse control valve openings equipped with a servo motor from Festo, with a current price per unit of approximately 1000 USD. Over the last two decades, numerous improvements have been made in LoaD applications, including innovative passive valving methods and multiple inline siphons that utilize a single disc for multiple test setups, as described in Ducrée (2021b, pp. 1-10). It promises many increased diagnostic solutions, which promises a speedup and cost reduction.

2.4.4. LoaC and LoaD Technologies in Livestock

Regulatory Conditions for Point-of-care Testing in Veterinary Environment In Flatland et al. (2013), it is noted that regulations are often missed for veterinarian clinics, and quality control is typically left to the profession itself. The Society for Veterinary Clinical Pathology (ASVCP) guidelines are recommended to improve POC testing in veterinary medicine, especially by implementing an overarching laboratory quality management program. Regulations in Japan for POCT are similar to human in vitro testing. In the European Union, there are no regulations. In the United States, POCT, in general, falls under the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), but veterinary POCT is not covered by a mandatory prior authorization, as shown in POTOCKOVA et al. (2020).

Potential for Livestock Vidic et al. (2017) considers the high test time from traditional methods makes it worthwhile to invest efforts in developing POC biosensing systems for livestock and poultry for pathogen detection. The statement about POC

“They are designed to be portable, user-friendly, simple to use, and usually have a turnaround time from sample to result in under an hour, allowing diagnosis and management decisions to be initiated within the same encounter [Hobbs et al. \(2021, p. 1836\)](#)”, and pointing to various existing POCs with different test techniques shows that the potential for Livestock is given.

Challenges in Livestock Respecting that POC testing has become popular for standard medical practice [Manassis et al. \(2022, pp. 25-26\)](#) by referencing [Bossis \(2019\)](#), it discusses that the introduction and familiarizing farmers with new technologies like POC with implementations like LoAD is crucial, especially since farmers are often skeptical of new technologies. Another challenge is the lack of mass production, which results in too high costs [Chin et al. \(2012\)](#). The required easy user handling, limitations of reagent access, and clear result interpretations are noted as additional challenges.

Challenges in Diagnostic Validity Studies [Manassis et al. \(2022, pp. 25\)](#) mention that most studies for POCT tends to be too optimistic by referencing to [Hobbs et al. \(2020\)](#) which again references to [Cohen et al. \(2016\)](#) which again reference to a paper from 2006 which states: “The use of data-driven cut points exaggerates test performance in many simulated data sets, and this bias probably affects many published diagnostic validity studies. [Ewald \(2006\)](#)”. Whether this, after almost 20 years, remains applicable is difficult to confirm or refute. It is possible that many of the newer studies already respect these findings and try to mitigate this effect by test setup or mathematical corrections. It is outside the scope of this thesis. Still, it highlights the difficulties in gathering data for new health applications, and even more so for livestock, because patients cannot directly communicate with testers and researchers.

2.4.5. Comparing Between XPOCT and POC to Central Laboratories

In [Figure 1.2](#), an ideal xPOCT and an estimated ideal POCT device are compared with central laboratories. In this section, the current available POCT or xPOCT will be compared with central laboratories. Shown in [Manassis et al. \(2022\)](#), one of the

significant advantages of POCT and xPOCT is, that fast access to results changes the conditions for disease outbreaks. It helps mitigate the risk of disease outbreaks in high-scale farming. Without specifying the operational definitions and instrument class, it is not possible to make a clear comparison between POCT/xPOCT versus centralized laboratories. Given that this research focuses on market needs to develop the disc setup and techniques, a theoretical selection of a POC or xPOC device adds no value to the work output.

2.5. A LoAD Benefits, Risk, Mitigation Overview

The previous sections introduced what is possible and promising in various technologies and test strategies. It highlights the need for more testing in livestock to benefit both human and animal well-being and reduce mortality related to zoonotic diseases in humans. [Velayudhan and Naikare \(2022\)](#) also highlights the increasing market need. They highlight the need for careful validation and high standards in quality for the tests and devices, even though they state “There is no adequate validation standards or regulatory requirements [Velayudhan and Naikare \(2022, p. 7\)](#)”. The article lists a comprehensive table of commercially available POCT diagnostics for infectious diseases, and for which specific animal species it is applicable.

benefits of Using Point-of-Care Testing (POCT) In [Table 2.4](#), the benefits of using POCT, often employing microfluidics and implemented through LoAD tests, along with accompanying risks and potential mitigation strategies, are listed.

Dimension	Anticipated Benefits/Key Drivers	Associated Risks/Barriers	Mitigation Strategies/What Needs to Happen
Economic	Reduced mortality and cattle weight loss (Railey and Marsh, 2021); decreased transport costs per sample; reduced antibiotic costs (Section 2.1 and 2.6)	High upfront device costs (Chin et al., 2012); price sensitivity in narrow-margin livestock sector (Manassis et al., 2022); predicted higher costs per test	Cooperative ownership models; pay-per-test pricing; decreasing test costs through test kit production innovation; cost-benefit demonstrations
Operational	60-minute results vs. days-to-weeks turnaround (Francis, 2022; Hobbs et al., 2021); reduced sample transport costs; improved herd management efficiency (Section 2.3 and 2.4.5)	Equipment failure in harsh field conditions; maintenance complexity; fragility in field conditions	Robust device design for field conditions; local technical support networks; preventive maintenance protocols
Antimicrobial Stewardship	Targeted antibiotic therapy (Horvat and Kovačević, 2025); reduced preventive antibiotic use; targeted antibiotic use reduces misuse (Section 2.1 and 2.1.1)	False negatives leading to untreated infections; over-reliance on test results	Clinical decision support algorithms; veterinary teleconsultation integration; treatment protocol guidelines

Continued on next page

Dimension	Anticipated Benefits/Key Drivers	Associated Risks/Barriers	Mitigation Strategies/What Needs to Happen
User Adoption	Farmer autonomy in health management (Velayudhan and Naikare, 2022); immediate diagnostic capabilities; enables farmer autonomy (Section 2.6)	Resistance to new technology (Manassis et al., 2022); complexity of operation; misinterpretation of results; skill gap (Railey and Marsh, 2021)	Simplified interfaces; comprehensive training programs; farmer demonstrations; field repetitions for veterinarians and farmers
Regulatory	Speed enhances outbreak control (Crisuolo et al., 2025); improved disease surveillance capabilities	Lack of animal POCT standards (Flatland et al., 2013); inconsistent guidelines across regions	Advocate for clear guidelines; engage with regulatory bodies
Infrastructure	Reduced dependence on centralized laboratory infrastructure; adaptability to resource-limited settings (Michael et al., 2016); improved accessibility in remote areas (Section 2.3 and 2.6)	Unreliable internet connectivity; limited trained personnel; poor road conditions (Hobbs et al., 2021)	Offline-capable systems; local training programs; robust packaging; mobile testing support

Table 2.4.: Comprehensive Benefits, Risks, and Mitigation Framework for LoAD Implementation in Livestock Diagnostics

2.6. Indicators for Market Needs for Livestock Diagnostics

The study in [Vudriko et al. \(2021\)](#) is related to Uganda, a developing country in Africa, with its country-specific challenges and conditions. Yet, it still offers insights into potential market needs in Paraguay, a country in South America. Based on the survey, the most common challenges for diagnostic laboratory services are a lack of necessary equipment and reagents, as well as the use of reagents that are either too expensive or unsuitable for their intended purpose. The survey also found that many laboratories have too few employees or staff who lack proper training.

In [Manassis et al. \(2022, pp. 25-26\)](#), the price sensitivity in livestock is highlighted due to the narrow margin bandwidths, which means POC devices need to target the lower price segment. Because the massive use of tests to prevent outbreaks is crucial, if one disc can be used to test multiple cattle, it would drive down the price per cattle and make it more attractive.

Economic Impact Research in the United States by [Railey and Marsh \(2021\)](#) shows that when anaplasmosis enters a herd, a tick-borne disease (see external parasites [Section 2.1](#) as well) reduces body weight by a range of 20% to 30%. It shows the eminent economic impact.

Need for Field Tests There exist field tests for zoonotic and other important animal diseases, but it is mentioned that POCT evaluations are rarely performed in the field, where the biggest impact is predicted ([Railey and Marsh, 2021](#)).

2.7. Current State of Research Related to Research Questions

[Table 2.5](#) provide a synthesis of how existing research addresses the study's research questions. It identifies remaining knowledge gaps that require investigation.

Research Question	Research finding	Identified gap	Link to dissertation
RQ1: Current live-stock diagnostic practices, gaps and needs in Paraguay	Global studies show distance to veterinary laboratories is the dominant barrier to sample submission	No baseline data exist on Paraguayan farmers' testing frequency, service-utilization patterns or actual laboratory capacity. Field survey required to establish diagnostics work-flow benchmarks.	Section 2.3
RQ2: Diseases that would benefit most from POC / LoaD	High-priority conditions for rapid testing include gastrointestinal nematodes (\approx 15.6 billion USD annual losses in Brazil + USA), FMD, brucellosis, BVDV. LoaD platforms already run LAMP, PCR and ELISA assays with <60 min turnaround	No LoaD validation yet for Paraguay's specific pathogen strains or sample matrices	Section 2.4.3 & 2.1
RQ3: Stakeholder groups with the highest early-adoption potential	Literature points that farmers are often skeptical of new technologies.	No segmentation data for Paraguayan stakeholder landscape, to quantify early-adopter pool.	Section 2.4.4

Continued on next page

Research Question	Research finding	Identified gap	Link to dissertation
RQ4: Cultural factors, trust and information flow	Farmer scepticism toward new technologies. Paraguayan political context marked by high inequality and oligopolistic land-ownership (3% own 90% land)	Specific cultural norms, decision heuristics and trust dynamics of Paraguayan livestock communities remain unstudied.	Section 1.1.3 & 2.4.4
RQ5: Business models/pricing strategies are economically viable	Livestock operations are conducted on narrow margins. Cooperative ownership and pay-per-test pricing are mentioned by the author as promising models.	No cost-benefit modeling has been conducted yet for Paraguayan herd sizes or farm structures. Acceptable prices are unknown.	Section 2.6
RQ6: Training, support, and infrastructure necessary for implementation	Simplified user interfaces and structured training shown essential for successful POC deployment. Ugandan survey highlights lack of equipment, reagents, and trained staff as key bottlenecks.	Paraguay-specific training effort, digital readiness, and support-infrastructure requirements for POC and LoAD remain undefined.	Section 2.6 & 2.2

Table 2.5.: Literature synthesis and gap analysis for research questions

3. Methodology

In the chapter, the methodology is divided into distinct process states to address the objectives and research questions in [Sections 1.4](#) and [1.5](#). Beginning with the philosophy, justification, and recruitment for data gathering. The survey architecture itself, including piloting. The gathered data will be analyzed through sampling and coding, and then abstracted by theming. Finally, an ethical review will critically examine the proposed workflow, including the questionnaire.

3.1. Research Philosophy

Overall sympathizing with Objectivism the author show stronger tendency to compare new information with natural science and physical laws and mathematical concept trying to be value-free, as long it is possible to recognizable with all the own blind-spots, and see it as an success if a generalization could be found, deeper explained and compared with the other ontology subjectivism in [Saunders et al. \(2023, pp. 134-139\)](#) In this thesis, a pragmatist philosophy approach is elaborated. Because it is a complex area. [Saunders et al. \(2023, pp. 146-147\)](#) mentioned that this is an indicator to use pragmatism. In this research, multiple stakeholders with diverse educational backgrounds and levels are involved, and no state-of-the-art techniques are employed. With the additional challenge of conducting it in a developing country, it is essential to find numbers and facts, as well as address the doubts of farmers and veterinarians. The relationship to questions is explained in the next section.

3.2. Justification of the Method

To address the research questions in [Sections 1.5](#), the study explores the topic and market area with open questions, too, to identify gaps and barriers that may not be

apparent during the preparation of this survey. By choosing pragmatist philosophy, the interpretivist focuses on understanding the meanings and challenges from stakeholders, acknowledging that farmers have individual perspectives on their challenges and issues. The positivism part supports an algorithm-driven analysis to identify tendencies and prepare them for later critical analysis. It is also crucial to determine some key numbers and bandwidth for pricing, acceptance, and other factors to get insights of values and distribution, thereby gaining a better understanding of the market.

3.3. Interview and Survey Design

To fulfill the needs of end-users, veterinarians and farmers are the primary stakeholders; their needs, struggles, knowledge, and perspectives are essential for a better understanding of the research. The chosen strategy is a survey, collecting data through the method of a questionnaire, which will handle a larger amount of diversity by addressing the heterogeneous group of farmers and the different needs introduced in [Figure 1.3](#). When the interviewee struggles with reading, the interviewer will guide them through the questionnaire and complete it for them. In that case, it is a structured interview. According to [Kumar \(2019, pp. 153–168\)](#), a questionnaire offers benefits such as lower costs and reduced time intensity. For example, with the method of observation, it takes several months for each farm to observe how they handle diseases in their herd. In this thesis, the questionnaire also respects the time constraints of the veterinarian. They can do it entirely on their own, on their schedule. The chosen compromise, to conduct structured interviews with some farmers ([Kumar, 2019, pp. 154–155](#)), also referred to as “interviewer-completed questionnaires” in [Saunders et al. \(2023, pp. 510–511\)](#), is more time-consuming. For all that, it also respects this vital group and increases trustworthiness by gathering data from different perspectives. The interview is guided through the same questions in the exact order as the questionnaire.

3.3.1. Finding Theories Throughout the Gathered Data

It is expected that some clear trends will emerge from the data gathered. This means that some questions exhibit a significant trend, which will be analyzed using standard mathematical approaches with a 90% confidence interval related to the

group size. While it requires 323 fulfilled questionnaires to detect a significant difference with a 95% confidence interval on a question with 30% saying yes and 70% saying no, the required fulfilled questionnaires decreases to 58 with a 90% confidence interval. Franz et al. (2021, p. 70) discusses that the 90% confidence interval use, depending on the variables and aim, can be sufficient. Given the early market need and barriers in livestock, it is decided to work with a 90% confidence interval. Harrington (1981) mentioned that for a homogeneous farmer group, around 50 questionnaires are enough. It is expected that the small farms are not necessarily homogeneous with the middle and large farms. Therefore, at least 150 fulfilled questionnaires are targeted. One of the assumptions is that a few answers will correlate with the questions about herd size and type (question A1 and A2) of livestock. In Chapter 5 the results are discussed.

3.3.2. Questionnaire Clusters and Descriptions

Related to the described complexity above in 3.1, it is explained why a pragmatist approach is chosen. To organize the questions, the author clusters questions into the following ten thematic clusters (A–J):

1. **Farm Profile and Operations** – herd size, livestock type, testing frequency, disease concerns.
2. **Current Practices and Experience** – systematically optimizing, testing execution, testing method requirements.
3. **Barriers and Adoption Potential** – reason no use, testing openness, adopting concerns.
4. **Economic Considerations and Preferences** – pricing expectations, investment thresholds, payment models, antibiotic reduction willingness, self testing.
5. **Trust, Value, and Decision-Making** – certification trust, premium pricing willingness, accuracy tolerance, test availability time, data sharing willingness.
6. **Information Sources and Communication Channels** – advisory networks, communication preferences, farmer associations, cooperative trust, trying willingness.
7. **Regulatory and Compliance Awareness** – regulatory familiarity, compliance importance.
8. **Innovation Adoption Profile** – learning paths, adoption factors, digital readiness, early adoption motivators.

9. **Livestock Health Priorities and Disease Concerns** – economic disease impact, health management challenges, early detection importance.
10. **Operational Context and Infrastructure** – veterinary access, internet connectivity, trained personnel, self-testing capability.

Attention for Proper Questioning Careful attention was paid to formulating neutral, concise, and unambiguous questions, with each question addressing a single point and time-related inquiries confined to a specified timeframe.

3.3.3. Question Types

In this section, the questions are categorized into closed questions, scaled questions, and open questions. [Table 3.1](#) further refines these three basic types according to the number of possible answers.

Question type	Question links
Closed [Yes, No], [Yes, No, Depends on conditions]	[B1, B2, C2, D4, E1, E2, E3, E5, F3, F4, H5, J1a, J1b, J4]
Closed [Number], [Word], [Category]	[A1, A2, A3, C3, C4, D1a, D1b, D2, D3, D5, F1, F2, H2, H4, I2, J1, J2, J3]
Closed [List of words]	[A4, A5, B3, C1, I1]
scaled [1...5]	[E4, F5, G1, G2, H3, I3]
Open question	[C2a, D4a, E1a, H1, I2]
Showing do not answer is fine	[E1a, G1, G2]

Table 3.1.: Overview question type

3.4. Piloting

Four experts review the draft survey. The experts' backgrounds are described in [Table 3.2](#). They have insight into the agricultural market and business, live science experience, and human engineering knowledge, strengthened by working with

Paraguayan communities in the agricultural sector.

Background	Cultural background	Years of work experience	Years in Paraguay
Agrar econome and investor	foreigner	over 15	8
Engineer in Human Ecology	Paraguayan	15	not applicable
Engineer, Researcher, Data Scientist, Professor	foreigner	10	3
Agricultural Management	Paraguayan	5	not applicable

Table 3.2.: Overview of the survey reviewer and expert group

3.5. Recruitment

Through the reviewers, a broader network of farmers and veterinarians is reachable. Beginning on 31. July, a twice-daily International Congress on Bovine Nutrition, with an estimated hundreds of veterinarians participating from all over the country. The author plans to attend this congress to gather additional interviewees. The following week, the focus is on collecting data from the rural side, mostly from farmers. Following the first 30 questionnaires submitted after the congress, an analysis test run will be conducted to review the data. To have the opportunity for a break if it becomes apparent that the data would not be usable, due to unclear questions or other issues, before the costly and intensive data gathering begins on the rural side. The schedule is visualized as a [Gantt chart 3.1](#).

Many farmers are unable to read. That was one of the key findings from the piloting. Therefore, an interviewer who goes through the questionnaire with them is required. Interviewers are hired by students who participate in an agriculture-related program at a University and/or by the independent US government agency, the Peace Corps.

The questionnaire is available in digital, over www.limesurvey.org, and print form. Depending on the area, the Paraguayans speak Spanish or Guarani, rarely English. Therefore, the questionnaire will be translated from the Paraguay government-approved translator to Spanish and Guarani. For quality control, it will be back-translated by another approved translator from each language into English. [Saun-](#)

ders et al. (2023, p. 538) assesses in Table 11.4 the “Back-translation” approach, the strength to detect most problems with a high likelihood. The author will verify this output against the source questionnaire to ensure quality, in collaboration with one of the piloting team members in Table 3.2.

Figure 3.1.: Gantt chart for the data gathering and analysis phase.

3.6. Sampling

Going through the flow chart in Saunders et al. (2023, p. 305), it makes sense to use non-probability sampling, because the ratio to the whole target is unknown. The author’s experience of data gathering for data analysis over the last three years in Paraguay for business analysis in the agricultural sector reveals a recognized lack of existing data, as well as higher skepticism regarding the correctness of available data. With support from one of the Paraguayan reviewers in Table 3.2, the available data confirm the author’s existing experiences. In Rural Association of Paraguay (2019), only an approximate number is provided from the government report (see Paragraph Paraguay cattle numbers in 1.1.3). Some families have only a few cattle in the poorest conditions. The high prices for official documents in Paraguay raise questions about whether they are accurately counted, and if so, whether they are registered regularly. Regarding that, it is not trustworthy to try to answer the research questions and findings with inferences for the complete market in Paraguay for cattle. Refusals and non-returns are not counted as a risk to bias the dataset. There may be a risk that a tendency exists for more innovative veterinarians and farmers to take the time to respond to the questions.

3.7. Coding

The qualitative questions [C2a, D4a, E1a, H1, I2] related to interpretivist research philosophy and the questions for gathering qualitative answers will be coded. One in [Table 3.2](#) listed experts will perform 10% of the coding and theming independently. After that, a comparison with the author's coding and theming should show the same result. In cases where it is not, it will be investigated to identify the root cause and discussed with the reviewer until the gap is closed.

3.8. Theming and Dataprocessing

The performed coding is the base for the theming list. The theme represents the final research output from the qualitative questions.

Both qualitative and quantitative answers will be processed with Python scripts prepared by the author. The quantitative answers will have a previous filtering step to remove outliers.

3.9. Ethics

The questionnaire will be reviewed by the supervisor delegated authority, guided by the formal Research Ethics Policy, which is approved by the Research & Knowledge Exchange Committee [Research and Knowledge Exchange Directorate \(2024\)](#).

The thesis has no intention of reducing employee workload, which could lead to layoffs or a decline in job satisfaction. The research aim in [Section 1.3](#) implies improvements for all stakeholders in daily life and for the well-being of the animals as well.

Interviewees have the opportunity not to answer questions that could bring them into an awkward situation by selecting the answer option “not answer”, and the interviewer will be trained for this. The related questions are shown in [Table 3.1](#).

Safeguards Interviewees The questionnaire respects the situation of farmers and veterinarians in the challenging country environment, especially the government environment, as explained in [Paraguayan market environment, in Section 1.1.3](#), by avoiding questions that could put them in a dilemma without warning. To sharpen awareness, four experts reviewed the questions, two of whom were Paraguayan and the other two foreigners with several years of work experience in Paraguay.

Data Security Personal data, such as name and birthdate, is not part of the survey and will not be stored. Additionally, this will not be achieved in another way, such as using information in the filenames or a meta table with corresponding traceability. These precautions guarantee as much anonymization as possible. The files will be stored on a password-protected Google Cloud storage account. Access is given to the author and, if requested, to the supervisor.

Publication The piloting reviewer and other interested stakeholders will be informed when the publication becomes available online.

4. Results and Findings

This chapter presents the results and findings from field research conducted in Paraguay to evaluate the potential for adopting Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) technology in livestock diagnostics.

4.1. Methodology Deviations and Data Gathering

The author administered questionnaires to farmers and veterinarians, which were organized into ten thematic clusters designed to address the six primary research questions. It is important to note that some methodological deviations occurred during the data gathering phase.

4.1.1. Methodology Deviations

The field implementation revealed several practical challenges that required methodological adaptations while maintaining the research integrity and validity.

Language Implementation Challenges: The initial bilingual strategy encountered unexpected complexities during rural deployment. Written Guarani proved problematic for survey participants, as the local variant represents primarily an oral tradition with significant Spanish integration, locally termed “Jopará”. During the first few surveys during a congress and in parallel in rural communities, farmers consistently responded more effectively to Spanish questionnaires accompanied by oral Guarani explanations when clarification was needed. Consequently, the author discontinued the online Guarani survey version and proceeded exclusively with Spanish questionnaires, while selecting interviewers with excellent Guarani qualifications and a high level of cultural context.

Questionnaire Refinement Process During the first twelve survey responses, it turned out that the question “D2” and “H2” needed the additional selection option “I do not measure” and “No experience”. Because for a few participants, none of the provided selections was applicable. This adaptation improved response accuracy by reducing forced choices that might not reflect participants’ actual opinions.

Interviewer Recruitment Adjustments The original plan to engage university students from agricultural programs as primary interviewers, encountered practical obstacles related to academic scheduling and rural accessibility. There were also doubts about their awareness and maturity to perform the questionnaire in a supportive yet non-intrusive manner.

Finally, the decision was made due these two reasons:

- Students from Universities that are relevant to this research were not available during the working week due to their obligatory class times.
- The demanding nature of rural data collection, including long travel distances, varying farm schedules, and the need for cultural sensitivity in approaching farming families, required more experienced personnel than initially anticipated.

Peace Corps Volunteer Engagement Limitations The active Peace Corps volunteers expressed their concerns about their Guarani proficiency for technical agricultural discussions. No volunteers were found, which led to a strategic shift in the recruitment of interviewers.

Implemented Helper Setup The author engaged two former Peace Corps volunteers with established experience in Paraguay and a deep cultural understanding of the country. Both lived with the farmer’s commune for over two years. They were supplemented by local veterinarians and agricultural economists who provided direct access to farming networks and professional credibility within the farm community.

Adoption Success The enhanced response options, based on the first few surveys, which served as a second pilot, improved data quality after consideration of the piloting group in [Table 3.2](#) by reducing response forcing by offering to select a

“unknown”. The interview recruitment adjustment increased trustworthiness in the quality and supported participants positively.

4.1.2. Data Gathering Implementation

As planned in the [Gantt chart 3.1](#), the hired veterinarian joined the congress on July 31st and August 1st, on the topic of cattle nutrition. It already indicated the difficulty in obtaining data. The helper was highly motivated, due to the topic and the opportunity for a higher fee if he reached more than 50 pieces. He talked with around a hundred congress attendees, out of nearly four hundred participants, during the two days, and personally motivated 10 survey participants. After that, to reach farmers at their places of work, the author visited in person, together with one of the helpers, farmer cooperatives, big slaughterhouses, as well as the University Asociación Rural del Paraguay (ARP), government offices from SENACSA, and other relevant institutions. From all these institutions, the author and his helper received the necessary assistance. For example, employees always guided them to the responsible person, such as the University president. One cooperative stakeholder hinted that she does not see a high success rate. The last time this group of partners conducted a critical survey, they received only three responses from the farmers. Prompted by this feedback, the author refocused on demonstrating the survey’s value to farmers and fine-tuning the outreach strategy. It will be an arduous journey to obtain enough fully completed surveys, which require more creativity and adaptability to achieve without compromising research standards.

Turn to More Success To hire relevant social media influencers from the farming community, written requests were sent to them, asking them to create a video encouraging their followers to fill out the survey; however, the author received no responses. Therefore, as the next try, the author’s business Instagram account for trail-runners with around 600 followers was used to spread a specially produced 37-second video that requested the runners, many of them are farmers or known some, to fulfill or share the survey, resulting in over 14,000 views, 300 side openings, many reshares, and even more likes. During this period, only two survey completions appeared. Finally, shop owners with an agricultural background were responsible for gathering a larger share of the survey by conducting the study with their clients in the shop, and they provided technical support to attend. Additionally, agrareconoms performed it during their farmers’ visits. They were highly motivated by the topic

and appreciated the potential value the research results could generate for Paraguay.

Impact on the Timeline The low survey response rate led to changes in the planned timeline in [Gantt chart 3.1](#). With a Python-driven, dynamically updated statistic, which helped analyze the data in parallel, the survey remained open to expand data collection. The parallelization is shown in the updated [Gantt chart 4.1](#).

Figure 4.1.: Effective performed data gathering and analysis phase.

Translation In questions with selections, the Spanish words were automated by the author's Python script, substituted from the original English survey. As planned in [Section 3.8](#). For the questions with free words, a Python dictionary was used. Similar Spanish words, sometimes only misspelled or with the same meaning in the farmer's own words, were translated with the same English word to get correct statistics. In response to potential concerns about specialized terms and diseases, the author consulted with experts from the piloting group, as listed in [Table 3.2](#).

Coding and Theming By open questions, the answers were first translated by a certified translator into English. After that, the author did the coding and theming. For quality proof, one participant of the piloting groups in [Table 3.2](#) conducted a partial independent coding and theming, and the results were compared.

4.2. Presentation of Results with Findings

In this section, the author presents results and findings, which will be discussed in the following [Chapter 5](#). The compact questions “yes/no/depends on condition” and “with a scale” are listed in the [Appendix B](#) for all categories. All other results are presented in tables without quantization, so the whole dataset. If a special insight or deviation related to the farm size or the farm type was found, it is separately mentioned or presented.

Survey Statistics This section presents the statistical analysis of the survey responses from Paraguay’s livestock sector regarding the potential for adopting Lab-on-a-Disc technology. There were 164 participants, 150 of whom completed the survey, and 14 did not finish it but filled out at least one page.

4.2.1. Full Data and Quantization

In [Table 4.1](#), the statistics of the participants with cattle are shown. There is a wide spread of herd size in the full-dataset. Due to the participation of many small farms, the median is low. On the other hand, the few large farms have a high number of cattle, which is why the mean value is far from the median, and the standard deviation (Std) is high. The P25¹ and P75² are better indicators to consider the bandwidth from farm sizes. [Section 4.2.2](#) presents more details.

¹ 25% of the data are below it

² 75% of the data are below it, and the remaining 25% above it

Answer	Full-dataset	Small	Medium	Large	Dairy	Meat
N (Answers)	147	51	48	48	39	93
Mean	460	34	176	1198	94	549
Std	940	28	53	1380	75	1085
Minimum	4	4	100	300	5	4
P25	50	11	130	442	40	80
Median	150	25	150	830	80	240
P75	420	50	240	1425	125	600
Maximum	9000	90	280	9000	315	9000

Table 4.1.: Category: Full-dataset. A1: How many animals do you own?

In Paraguay, veterinarians are also commonly owners of cattle. That is the reason why 150 participants, not 171, fulfilled the survey. Even though the sum of 147 participants who filled out the survey mentioned owning cattle and 24 mentioned they are veterinarians.

Quantization of Farm Size The author adapted the provided quantization shown in [Figure 4.2](#), a little after consulting two of the piloting group in [Table 3.2](#). Both mentioned an independent quantization bandwidth of below 100 for small farms, between 100 and 300 for medium farms, and above 300 for large farms. In [Rural Association of Paraguay \(2019, p. 5\)](#), the threshold is set at 100 as well, to note that 89% of herd sizes are below that threshold in Paraguay. To gather sufficient data for the three farm size categories, the survey deviates from the ratio of farm sizes in the Paraguayan market.

Figure 4.2.: Distribution of farms by cattle size categories. Small farms: 1-99 cattle (34.7%), Medium farms: 100-299 cattle (32.7%), Large farms: 300+ cattle (32.7%)

Quantization of Farm Type Figure 4.3 provides the statistics quantized by type, which were done for the types dairy and meat. Some only mentioned bovine or another unclear indication for one of these two types. They are presented as “other” in the plot and are excluded from all the analyses related to the farm types dairy and meat.

Figure 4.3.: Distribution of farms by type categories. Dairy farms: (26.5%), Meat farms: (63.3%), Other farms: (10.2%)

4.2.2. Cluster A: Farm Profile and Operations

Question A1 is significant to identify trends that depend on characteristics related to farm sizes. The quantization is presented in [Section 4.2.1](#). Within the farm size, the median and mean values are close to each other. The dairy category, which includes more small to medium-sized farms, has a close median and mean value. For the meat category, the distribution of farm sizes is significant. There are small farms with only a few cattle, which help the family get enough food for the day, up to big farms with many employees. Therefore, the median and mean values are far apart.

Question A2 answers are based on the type of livestock farming, resulting in two main groups: meat and dairy production. For quantization, see the previous [Section 4.2.1](#), and the counted farm types are presented in [Table 4.2](#). More meat producers participated, in [Rural Association of Paraguay \(2019, p. 5\)](#), the beef sector was quantized by 90%. To gather sufficient data for dairy farms, the survey deviates from the ratio of dairy and meat farms in the Paraguayan market.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Dairy (dairy)	27	18.2%	
Bovine (meat)	26	17.6%	
Fattening (meat)	19	12.8%	
Breeding/Raising (meat)	17	11.5%	
Bovine (not specified)	14	9.5%	
Dual Purpose (meat *)	12	8.1%	
Holstein (dairy)	10	6.8%	
Creole (meat *)	7	4.7%	
Brahman (meat)	5	3.4%	
Common (meat)	3	2.0%	
Jersey (dairy)	3	2.0%	
Nelore (meat)	2	1.4%	
Bull	1	0.7%	
Zebu (meat)	1	0.7%	
Brangus (meat)	1	0.7%	

Table 4.2.: Category: Full-dataset. A2: What type of livestock do you have?

* In Paraguay, in a dual purpose, the milk is mainly used to feed the calves, not for business

Question A3 presents in [Table 4.3](#) no clear tendencies regarding how often farms test their livestock for health monitoring. The most frequently mentioned method is “seasonally”. A remark, 75% with daily testing are in the category of dairy farms. An interpretation of two of the piloting experts from [Table 3.2](#) is, that they perform a visual check, not a laboratory test. The visual test is only feasible if the cattle remain in the same place all the time, or at least overnight, which is the case in a dairy system during the milking process for cows, as explained by the same experts.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Daily	12	8.0%	
Weekly	14	9.3%	
Monthly	31	20.7%	
Seasonally	53	35.3%	
Annually	30	20.0%	
Never	9	6.0%	
No Answer	1	0.7%	

Table 4.3.: Category: Full-dataset. A3: How often do you currently test your livestock for health monitoring?

Question A4 contains rich data on livestock disease. In dairy and meat farms, there are different ranks as well within the categories of Full-dataset, small, medium, and large farms, as seen in [Tables 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, and 4.9](#).

The specific livestock diseases that concern farmers most depend on the categories. Mastitis is with 3.9% ([Table 4.9](#)) in meat farms, rarely mentioned, and in dairy farms ([Table 4.8](#)) at the top with 27%. The finding is consistent with the article [Campbell \(2013\)](#), which mentions That Mastitis is often an issue for dairy farms. In meat farms, it is still frequently overlooked or undiagnosed.

“Brucellosis” and “Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)” are very present. That is a attention-grabbing result, because a nationally supported vaccination is widely endorsed and strictly administered, and these two diseases should not often occur; more about that will be discussed in [Chapter 5](#).

A note on the tables: The author performed clustering analysis to obtain more meaningful statistics. The words listed in the caption from [Table 4.4](#) for each cluster apply to [Questions A4, A5 and I1](#). Not all words are always in each question and category mentioned by the participants. As the single listings produce no beneficial value, they are only shown in question A4 of the full-dataset statistics. This additional statistical analysis in the table was conducted to show the reader the full range of responses to questions with open-ended words. To keep the statistics clearly arranged, the author does not further distinguish them. He compares the

clusters against other diseases or clusters.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Brucellosis	58	14.3%	
Mastitis	41	10.1%	
Piroplasmosis	36	8.9%	
Diarrheal Diseases #	36	8.9%	
Clostridial Diseases ##	31	7.7%	
Leptospirosis	24	5.9%	
Nutritional/Management Issues ###	19	4.7%	
Respiratory Diseases ####	17	4.2%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	17	4.2%	
Anthrax	16	4.0%	
Others *	16	4.0%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases **	15	3.7%	
Metabolic Diseases ***	15	3.7%	
Parasitic Diseases	14	3.5%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	12	3.0%	
Anaplasmosis	9	2.2%	

Continued on next page

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	7	1.7%	■
Tuberculosis	7	1.7%	■
Pododermatitis	6	1.5%	■
Non-specific Clinical Signs	5	1.2%	■
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)****	4	1.0%	■

Table 4.4.: Category: Full-dataset. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

* Ticks (count 3), Neosporosis (2), Actinomycosis (2), Trichomoniasis (2), Intoxication (2), Goiter (1), External Parasites/Infestations (1), Omphalitis (1), Cystitis (1), Campylobacteriosis (1). Note: only in the full-dataset statistics separately listed with counts

** Metritis, Reproductive Diseases, Retained Placenta, Abortion, Leucosis

*** Hypocalcemia, Ruminal acidosis, Ketosis, Decalcification

**** Papillomas, enfermedades virosicas. Note: Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) is a Viral disease, too, but is often mentioned and therefore listed separately

Enteritis, Diarrheas, Neonatal diarrhea

Botulism, Blackleg, Clostridial Diseases, Tetanus

Bloat, Lack of Feeding, Nutritional, Due to Cold, Digestive Diseases, Tympanism, Meteorism, Deficiency diseases

Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis, Pneumonia, Viral Respiratory Diseases

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Mastitis	20	15.2%	
Piroplasmosis	17	12.9%	
Diarrheal Diseases	13	9.8%	
Brucellosis	11	8.3%	
Clostridial Diseases	9	6.8%	
Others	7	5.3%	
Parasitic Diseases	7	5.3%	
Metabolic Diseases	7	5.3%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	6	4.5%	
Leptospirosis	6	4.5%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	5	3.8%	
Anthrax	4	3.0%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	4	3.0%	
Non-specific Clinical Signs	4	3.0%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	3	2.3%	
Pododermatitis	3	2.3%	
Respiratory Diseases	3	2.3%	
Anaplasmosis	1	0.8%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	1	0.8%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	1	0.8%	

Table 4.5.: Category: Small-Farms. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Brucellosis	24	18.0%	
Diarrheal Diseases	16	12.0%	
Mastitis	16	12.0%	
Respiratory Diseases	11	8.3%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	10	7.5%	
Piroplasmiasis	9	6.8%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	8	6.0%	
Tuberculosis	7	5.3%	
Clostridial Diseases	5	3.8%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	5	3.8%	
Leptospirosis	5	3.8%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	3	2.3%	
Anthrax	3	2.3%	
Metabolic Diseases	3	2.3%	
Others	3	2.3%	
Anaplasmosis	2	1.5%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	1	0.8%	
Pododermatitis	1	0.8%	
Non-specific Clinical Signs	1	0.8%	

Table 4.6.: Category: Medium-Farms. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Brucellosis	22	17.5%	
Clostridial Diseases	17	13.5%	
Leptospirosis	13	10.3%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	10	7.9%	
Anthrax	8	6.3%	
Piroplasmosis	8	6.3%	
Parasitic Diseases	7	5.6%	
Others	6	4.8%	
Anaplasmosis	6	4.8%	
Diarrheal Diseases	5	4.0%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	5	4.0%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	4	3.2%	
Metabolic Diseases	4	3.2%	
Mastitis	3	2.4%	
Respiratory Diseases	3	2.4%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	2	1.6%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	1	0.8%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	1	0.8%	
Pododermatitis	1	0.8%	

Table 4.7.: Category: Large-Farms. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Mastitis	30	27.0%	
Brucellosis	18	16.2%	
Metabolic Diseases	9	8.1%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	9	8.1%	
Piroplasmosis	8	7.2%	
Leptospirosis	7	6.3%	
Diarrheal Diseases	7	6.3%	
Clostridial Diseases	6	5.4%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	4	3.6%	
Others	3	2.7%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	2	1.8%	
Pododermatitis	2	1.8%	
Respiratory Diseases	2	1.8%	
Anthrax	2	1.8%	
Non-specific Clinical Signs	1	0.9%	
Parasitic Diseases	1	0.9%	

Table 4.8.: Category: Dairy-Farms. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Brucellosis	29	12.5%	
Diarrheal Diseases	24	10.3%	
Piroplasmosis	22	9.5%	
Clostridial Diseases	19	8.2%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	18	7.8%	
Leptospirosis	14	6.0%	
Respiratory Diseases	13	5.6%	
Others	11	4.7%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	11	4.7%	
Anthrax	11	4.7%	
Parasitic Diseases	10	4.3%	
Mastitis	9	3.9%	
Anaplasmosis	8	3.4%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	8	3.4%	
Tuberculosis	7	3.0%	
Metabolic Diseases	5	2.2%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	3	1.3%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	3	1.3%	
Pododermatitis	3	1.3%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	2	0.9%	
Non-specific Clinical Signs	2	0.9%	

Table 4.9.: Category: Meat-Farms. A4: What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?

Question A5 asks about other diseases which participants are most concerned about. It is similar to [Question A4](#) in that the ranks depend strongly on the category. Only “Diarrheal Diseases” is in all categories on rank one or two, visible in [Table 4.10](#) for full-dataset statistics. “Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)” was falling back, but “Brucellosis” is still intuitively overrepresented too and will be discussed more deeply in [Chapter 5](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Diarrheal Diseases	21	13.4%	
Brucellosis	17	10.8%	
Clostridial Diseases	13	8.3%	
Others *	12	7.6%	
Piroplasmosis	12	7.6%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	11	7.0%	
Mastitis	8	5.1%	
Tuberculosis	8	5.1%	
Metabolic Diseases	7	4.5%	
Leptospirosis	7	4.5%	
Parasitic Diseases	6	3.8%	
Respiratory Diseases	6	3.8%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	6	3.8%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	5	3.2%	
Anthrax	5	3.2%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	5	3.2%	
Intoxication	4	2.5%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	4	2.5%	

Table 4.10.: Category: Full-dataset. A5: Besides this disease in the previous question, what other disease or diseases do you concern most?
 * Anaplasmosis (2), Cystitis (2), Infertility (2), Neosporosis (2), Ticks (count 1), Actinomycosis (1), Omphalitis (1), Campylobacteriosis (1)
 Note: for all other clusters see caption from [Table 4.4](#)

4.2.3. Cluster B: Current Practices and Experience

Question B1 shows no clear trend. Small farmers answered with 45% with “Yes”, that they conducted blood tests previously to optimize their herd’s health systematically. Farm for dairy type answered with 85% over the Full-dataset average with 71% ³.

Question B2 shows a clear trend to perform a blood test by themselves (“Yes” or “Depends on Condition”) on the farm to get the result faster than sending it to the laboratory⁴.

Question B3 “Ease of Use”, “Price”, “Validity”, and being “Fast” are the most frequently mentioned requirements for using a provided testing method. Like with the disease, a cluster analysis was performed to obtain more meaningful statistics. The clusters are listed in the caption of [Table 4.11](#).

³ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

⁴ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Ease of Use	87	26.3%	
Price	84	25.4%	
Validity *	76	23.0%	
Fast	55	16.6%	
Access-Related Barriers **	8	2.4%	
Process/Procedural Barriers ***	7	2.1%	
Cost	6	1.8%	
Effective ****	5	1.5%	
Consumables	1	0.3%	
Wide Range of Results	1	0.3%	
Sampling	1	0.3%	

Table 4.11.: Category: Full-dataset. B3: What requirements would this testing method need to fulfill for you to use it? (e.g., accuracy, speed, ease of use, price, etc.)

* Precision, Reliability, Accuracy, Safety/Security

** Lack of Access, Laboratory Availability, Distance, Sample Transport, Always Use, remote access

*** Complexity, Delay in Test Delivery, Practicality, Conservation Methods, Time Constraints, Application Time, Response Time

**** Effective, Efficiency

4.2.4. Cluster C: Barriers and Adoption Potential

Question C1 the selection “Access-Related Barriers” is clearly leading, followed by “Cost”, “Process/Procedural Barriers”, and “Lack of Information” as reasons why participants have not used blood tests or diagnostics. In [Table 4.12](#), the clusters listed in the caption of [Table 4.11](#) are used. The same intention applies as introduced in [Question A4](#) in Paragraph, [A note on the tables](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Access-Related Barriers	69	35.8%	
Cost	39	20.2%	
Process/Procedural Barriers	36	18.7%	
Lack of Information	35	18.1%	
I don't see the need	6	3.1%	
Large Herd Size	2	1.0%	
Personnel/Staff Issues	2	1.0%	
Validity	1	0.5%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	1	0.5%	
Lack of Decision	1	0.5%	
Mastitis	1	0.5%	

Table 4.12.: Category: Full-dataset. C1: If you have not used such blood tests or diagnostics, what were the main reasons or obstacles? (e.g., cost, complexity, lack of information, lack of access, etc.)

Question C2 shows with 95% a clear trend to use a simple and cost-effective testing method if available ⁵.

Question C2a figures out by an open question what the reason is for using or not using that simple and cost-effective testing method. The answers after coding and theming are shown in [Table 4.13](#) and [4.14](#). Answers often go in the direction to improve “Health Management”, earn “Economic Benefits”, and as another frequently used reason to use it, the “Practical Implementation”. The three focal topics in “Practical Implementation” are:

- “Speed”: increase test, result, decision, and so on
- “Easy Use”: performing, interpret, easy access, and so on
- “Efficiency”: improve management, optimizing process, improve production

⁵ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

. Large farms would use this test mainly because of all three aspects of “Practical Implementation”. To not use it “Technical Doubts” and a “Negative Performance Impact” concern is mentioned, while 5 of these seven concerns come from small farms. “Economic Benefits” was only set in theming if it was directly addressed. Behind “Practical Implementation” and “Health Management” lies an economic driver too. The primary reason for using a test is when a financial benefit is expected.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Health Management	49	23.9%	
Practical Implementation (Speed)	47	22.9%	
Economic Benefits	38	18.5%	
Practical Implementation (Easy Use)	36	17.6%	
Practical Implementation (Efficiency)	28	13.7%	
Technical Doubts	4	2.0%	
Negative Performance Impact	3	1.5%	

Table 4.13.: Category: Full-dataset. C2a: What is the reason of using or do not using it?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Practical Implementation (Speed)	17	26.2%	
Practical Implementation (Efficiency)	15	23.1%	
Practical Implementation (Easy Use)	12	18.5%	
Economic Benefits	11	16.9%	
Health Management	10	15.4%	

Table 4.14.: Category: Large-Farms. C2a: What is the reason of using or do not using it?

Question C3 primary concern about adopting new diagnostic technologies is “Cost” selected by over 39% followed by “Complexity” and “Reliability”, as shown in [Table 4.15](#). For small farms and dairy farms, the “Cost” is 51% more relevant than for

the other categories. In large farms are “Reliability” with 39.6% and “Complexity” with 25% the top-ranked concerns in front of “Cost”.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Cost	59	39.3%	
Complexity	40	26.7%	
Reliability	36	24.0%	
Training requirements	8	5.3%	
Regulatory compliance	5	3.3%	
Other	2	1.3%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.15.: Category: Full-dataset. C3: What is your primary concern about adopting new diagnostic technologies?

Question C4 shows a wide distribution of willingness to invest in training to learning a new diagnostic test over all farm sizes and types. By joining the groups “6-10 hours” and “11-20 hours”, almost 47% say they are willing to spend between 6 and 20 hours, see [Table 4.16](#). Large farms responded with 29.2% indicating that they are willing to spend more than 40 hours.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
0-5 hours	43	28.7%	
6-10 hours	35	23.3%	
11-20 hours	35	23.3%	
21-40 hours	17	11.3%	
above 40 hours	20	13.3%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.16.: Category: Full-dataset. C4: How many hours of training would you be willing to invest in learning a new diagnostic test?

4.2.5. Cluster D: Economic Considerations and Preferences

Question D1 requests the willingness to pay for an individual test and what for a complete testing package per cattle. One outlier has been removed with an unrealistically high price. In the first part of the responses, some gave 5, 100 Guaranies or similar prices per test, which makes no sense, because one USD is worth over 7000 Gs. Due to the weak currency, people in Paraguay often use the first number without mentioning the following thousands. Therefore, in those very low amounts, the author corrected with a factor of 1000. After the training, the supporters who conducted the interviews ensured that this mistake did not occur again. All ratios between the 25th percentile (P25) and the 75th percentile (P75) are between factors 2 and 3. Only at small farms for “Price per individual test” exists a higher ratio. The [Tables 4.17](#) and [4.18](#) shows the statistics.

Statistic /Category*	Full-dataset	Small	Medium	Large	Dairy	Meat
N (Answers)	137	49	38	47	36	85
Mean	22173	28551	16842	20569	25306	18556
Std	28887	37709	23813	21188	41203	17487
Minimum	250	5000	500	250	5000	250
P25	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
Median	12000	20000	12000	15000	12500	12000
P75	20000	40000	15000	20000	21250	20000
Maximum	250000	250000	150000	100000	250000	100000

Table 4.17.: Category: Full-dataset. D1a: What would be an acceptable price for such a test for common economically significant livestock diseases you mentioned above: Price per individual test:

* Prices are in Gs (Guaranies)

Statistic /Category*	Full-dataset	Small	Medium	Large	Dairy	Meat
N (Answers)	129	45	38	43	35	81
Mean	130321	96889	99026	197988	93943	151586
Std	278963	58904	109962	464435	59956	347734
Minimum	1500	30000	15000	1500	25000	1500
P25	50000	50000	48500	50000	49000	50000
Median	75000	100000	60000	100000	80000	75000
P75	120000	120000	95000	150000	120000	100000
Maximum	3000000	250000	500000	3000000	250000	3000000

Table 4.18.: Category: Full-dataset. D1b: Price for a complete testing package per cattle:

* Prices are in Gs (Guaranies)

Question D2 shows that for 66.6% maximal 1% from annual turnover would be spent for diagnostic equipment. The mentioned “I do not know/I do not measure” is remarkable with 21.3%. This response with “unknown” is also high in large farms with 33.3%. The selections are shown in [Table 4.19](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
0-0.5 from annual turnover	71	47.3%	
0.5-1 from annual turnover	29	19.3%	
1-2 from annual turnover	13	8.7%	
2-5 from annual turnover	4	2.7%	
over 5 from annual turnover	1	0.7%	
I do not know/I do not measure	32	21.3%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.19.: Category: Full-dataset. D2: What is the maximum you would invest in diagnostic equipment related to your annual turnover?

Question D3 shows that 58% are willing to “Purchase” the equipment instead of “Pay-per-test” presented in [Table 4.20](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Purchase	87	58.0%	
Pay-per-test	38	25.3%	
Subscription model	1	0.7%	
Lease	19	12.7%	
Other	5	3.3%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.20.: Category: Full-dataset. D3: Would you prefer to purchase diagnostic equipment outright or pay per test?

Question D4 is interesting for the antibiotics resistance topic overall, with a positive answer of 92% if they would reduce antibiotic use if a simple test could determine the necessity and type of medication. While 100% of large farms answered

with “Yes” ⁶.

Question D4a asks for the reason to reduce or not reduce antibiotic use. “Treatment Optimization” is frequently the reason, “Antibiotic resistance” too. All answers after the coding and theming are visible in [Table 4.21](#). From the 12 who answered in [Question D4](#) with “No” answered 5 with “No, use antibiotics mostly/always helpful”, the same 5 are all in the group small farm. This answer represents 9.5% of the group shown in [Table 4.22](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Treatment Optimization	104	47.7%	
Economic Efficiency	56	25.7%	
Antibiotic resistance	49	22.5%	
No, use antibiotics mostly/always helpful	8	3.7%	
Increasing revenue	1	0.5%	

Table 4.21.: Category: Full-dataset. D4a: What is the reason of reduce or do not reduce it?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Treatment Optimization	36	48.6%	
Economic Efficiency	18	24.3%	
Antibiotic resistance	13	17.6%	
No, use antibiotics mostly/always helpful	7	9.5%	

Table 4.22.: Category: Small-Farms. D4a: What is the reason of reduce or do not reduce it?

Question D5 shows 78.7% would perform Point-of-Care (POC) test by themselves shown in [Table 4.23](#). In the small farm is it less with 58.8%, and in dairy farms

⁶ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

higher with 87.2%.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Self	118	78.7%	
Service	31	20.7%	
No Answer	1	0.7%	

Table 4.23.: Category: Full-dataset. D5: As a farmer, would you prefer to operate a Point-of-Care (POC) test yourself or use an external service that isn't available around the clock?

4.2.6. Cluster E: Trust, Value, and Decision-Making

Question E1 was with 88% selected that trustiness increased by purchasing the animal came with certified test results, and an additional 9% answered with “Depends on condition” ⁷. In dairy farms, all 39 answered with “Yes”.

Question E1a is related to **Question E1** and ask for the reason why it increases or does not increase their trust, “Preventing spread” of disease and “Information and confidence” are the most mentioned. “Costs benefits” was chosen in coding and theming only if the answer directly addressed price, costs, purchase, profit, and so on. Behind the two leading motivations, “Preventing spread” and “Information and confidence”, is also an economic benefit in mind. While in large and dairy farms, “Information and confidence” is at the top and more motivating than “Preventing spread”. See the [Tables 4.25](#) and [4.24](#).

⁷ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Preventing spread	56	41.8%	
Information and confidence	52	38.8%	
Costs benefits	10	7.5%	
Depends on test Reliability and Context	7	5.2%	
no improvment	4	3.0%	
Animal well-being	3	2.2%	
Depending on trust in the testing institution	2	1.5%	

Table 4.24.: Category: Full-dataset. E1a: What is the reason of increase trust or why it does not increase your trust, or what would be the condition which it depends?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Information and confidence	20	55.6%	
Preventing spread	12	33.3%	
Costs benefits	3	8.3%	
Animal well-being	1	2.8%	

Table 4.25.: Category: Dairy-Farms. E1a: What is the reason of increase trust or why it does not increase your trust, or what would be the condition which it depends?

Question E2 represents the willingness to pay a higher price for livestock that has certified test results, which 86% answered with “Yes”⁸. The higher payment willingness is reasonable and corresponds to the substantial increase in truth mentioned in [Question E1](#).

⁸ Details see in Appendix [B.1](#)

Question E3 shows that 94% of respondents consider a test provided accuracy of 90% as beneficial and would use it. Large-, and dairy farms consider it with 100%⁹.

Question E4 shows on a Scale from 1-5, with an average score of 4.73¹⁰, participants see it as very important that test results are immediately available on-site.

Question E5 shows that 83% want to share anonymized test results with search institutions to improve livestock health, and additional 13% answered with “Depends on Condition”¹¹.

4.2.7. Cluster F: Information Sources and Communication Channels

Question F1 most answered to contact “Veterinarian” and with a larger distance on rank 2 “Fellow farmers” to consult when about livestock health management decisions are required. In the group dairy type, it is even more with 79.5% that the “Veterinarian” will be chosen. In the group meat farm, it is still high but less over “Veterinarian” and shifts to “Fellow farmers”, “Family members”, and “Online resources”, see [Tables 4.26, 4.28, and 4.27](#). In the conference [Grace et al. \(2008, p. 28\)](#), it is emphasized that trust in public veterinarians’ services, especially on small farms, is strong and prevalent.

⁹ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

¹⁰ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

¹¹ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

This constraint, low financial flexibility but more trust in the purchase, presents a challenging situation in finding a pricing model that fits.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Veterinarian	100	66.7%	
Fellow farmers	35	23.3%	
Government extension agent	3	2.0%	
Online resources	7	4.7%	
Family members	5	3.3%	
Other	0	0.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.26.: Category: Full-dataset. F1: Who do you consult most when making decisions about livestock health management?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Veterinarian	31	79.5%	
Fellow farmers	7	17.9%	
Government extension agent	1	2.6%	
Online resources	0	0.0%	
Family members	0	0.0%	
Other	0	0.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.27.: Category: Dairy-Farms. F1: Who do you consult most when making decisions about livestock health management?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Veterinarian	27	52.9%	
Fellow farmers	14	27.5%	
Government extension agent	0	0.0%	
Online resources	5	9.8%	
Family members	5	9.8%	
Other	0	0.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.28.: Category: Small-Farms. F1: Who do you consult most when making decisions about livestock health management?

Question F2 shows that the preferred method of receiving information about new agricultural technologies is “Face-to-face meetings” followed by “Social media”, without clear trends over the categories. The overview is shown in [Table 4.29](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Face-to-face meetings	79	52.7%	
Phone calls	10	6.7%	
Text messages	1	0.7%	
Email	5	3.3%	
Social media	19	12.7%	
Printed materials	14	9.3%	
Radio	1	0.7%	
Television	21	14.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.29.: Category: Full-dataset. F2: What is your preferred method of receiving information about new agricultural technologies?

Question F3 shows that 55% belong to any farmer associations or cooperatives. It is less than full-dataset for small farms with 35%, and is clearly more with 77% for dairy and medium farms¹².

Question F4 shows that by 65% the trust will be strengthened if a testing device is operated through the cooperative. It shows the same tendencies for small farms with below (45%) and dairy (85%) and medium (88%) above the other categories, like in [Question F3](#)¹³.

Question F5 shows the likelihood to try a new technology if recommended by a trusted veterinarian has an full-dataset average value of 4.48. Large farms show a higher likelihood than the other categories, with an average of 4.73¹⁴.

4.2.8. Cluster G: Regulatory and Compliance Awareness

Question G1 rated overall with an average value of 3.73, indicating that many are not familiar with current regulations. Large farms feel with 4.43 unusually high informed¹⁵, whereas small farms are with 2.65 below the medium of 3 on a scale from 1 to 5.

Question G2 has a similar pattern to the previous question. But the average value of how important it is that diagnostic technologies comply with national livestock regulations is 4.21. Large farms are with 4.73 unusually high neck and neck with medium farms (4.69)¹⁶.

4.2.9. Cluster H: Innovation Adoption Profile

Question H1 is an open question that shows how attendees typically learn about the existence of new agricultural technologies. It is led by “Professional advisors” and “Peer networks”, as visible in [Table 4.30](#). Small farms get more information

¹² Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

¹³ Details see in [Appendix B.1](#)

¹⁴ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

¹⁵ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

¹⁶ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

over “Peer networks” and “Social media”, and in a meat farm, “Peer networks” are on top before “Professional advisors”.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Professional advisors	62	31.2%	
Peer networks	54	27.1%	
Broadcast Media	31	15.6%	
Social media	31	15.6%	
Digital media	20	10.1%	
No access to information	1	0.5%	

Table 4.30.: Category: Full-dataset. H1: How do you typically learn about the existence of new agricultural technologies?

Question H2 shows that “Cost-benefit ratio” is, with 50%, the most crucial factor when deciding to adopt a new technology. For large farms it is different than the other categories “Proven effectiveness” (45.8%) comes before “Cost-benefit ratio” (39.6%). Data are shown in [Tables 4.31](#) and [4.32](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Proven effectiveness	48	32.0%	
Cost-benefit ratio	75	50.0%	
Ease of use	11	7.3%	
Peer recommendations	15	10.0%	
Regulatory approval	1	0.7%	
No experience	0	0.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.31.: Category: Full-dataset. H2: What is the most important factor when deciding to adopt a new technology?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Proven effectiveness	22	45.8%	
Cost-benefit ratio	19	39.6%	
Ease of use	2	4.2%	
Peer recommendations	5	10.4%	
Regulatory approval	0	0.0%	
No experience	0	0.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.32.: Category: Large-Farms. H2: What is the most important factor when deciding to adopt a new technology?

Question H3 shows that respondents feel comfortable using digital technologies in farming operations with an average value of 4.46, with all categories falling within a similar value ¹⁷.

Question H4 “Financial incentives” is the highest motivator to be the first to try a new livestock diagnostic technology, see [Table 4.33](#). “Peer testimonials” are also a motivator, and for large farms, even more critical, with 35.4% versus 27.1% for “Financial incentives” shown in [Table 4.34](#).

¹⁷ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Financial incentives	61	40.7%	
Free trial period	17	11.3%	
Training support	26	17.3%	
Peer testimonials	31	20.7%	
Scientific evidence	15	10.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.33.: Category: Full-dataset. H4: What would motivate you to be among the first to try a new livestock diagnostic technology?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Financial incentives	13	27.1%	
Free trial period	3	6.2%	
Training support	9	18.8%	
Peer testimonials	17	35.4%	
Scientific evidence	6	12.5%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.34.: Category: Large-Farms. H4: What would motivate you to be among the first to try a new livestock diagnostic technology?

Question H5 answered only 13% with “Yes” that they have heard of Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) diagnostic technology with no tendency for a category¹⁸.

¹⁸ Details see in Appendix B.1

4.2.10. Cluster I: Livestock Health Priorities and Disease Concerns

Question I1 was questioned to see if there are correlations to question A4 or A5. Both of these questions concern livestock diseases, which are the most concerning. In this question, the focus is on which diseases cause the most economic loss on a farm. It shows that “Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)” falls back in the rank. The high rank is highlighted in [Question A4](#). The rank of “Brucellosis” is still more present than expected. In large farms, the proportion is even overproportional at rank 1, at 25.4%, in medium farms at 13.4%, and in small farms at only 5.7%. In the top is “Mastitis” and “Piroplasmosis”, both are also in the top 3 in [Question A4](#). “Diarrheal Diseases” is on second rank in meat farms and is in dairy farms no cause for most economic loss. In the [Tables 4.35, 4.36 and 4.37](#) are the answers listed.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Mastitis	37	17.0%	
Brucellosis	30	13.8%	
Piroplasmosis	21	9.6%	
Diarrheal Diseases	18	8.3%	
Clostridial Diseases	15	6.9%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	14	6.4%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	13	6.0%	
Anthrax	12	5.5%	
Respiratory Diseases	11	5.0%	
Others *	11	5.0%	
Metabolic Diseases	9	4.1%	
Parasitic Diseases	7	3.2%	
Leptospirosis	6	2.8%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	5	2.3%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	3	1.4%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	3	1.4%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	3	1.4%	

Table 4.35.: Category: Full-dataset. I1: Which livestock diseases cause the most economic loss on your farm?

* Non-specific Clinical Signs (4), External Parasites/Infestations (3), Intoxication (1), Liver Diseases (1), Pododermatitis (1), Tuberculosis (1)

Note: for all other clusters see caption from Table 4.4

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Mastitis	29	48.3%	
Brucellosis	9	15.0%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	6	10.0%	
Metabolic Diseases	6	10.0%	
Piroplasmosis	4	6.7%	
Clostridial Diseases	3	5.0%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	1	1.7%	
Others	1	1.7%	
Diarrheal Diseases	1	1.7%	

Table 4.36.: Category: Dairy-Farms. I1: Which livestock diseases cause the most economic loss on your farm?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Brucellosis	20	15.7%	
Diarrheal Diseases	16	12.6%	
Nutritional/Management Issues	12	9.4%	
Piroplasmosis	12	9.4%	
Clostridial Diseases	11	8.7%	
Anthrax	11	8.7%	
Respiratory Diseases	10	7.9%	
Others	8	6.3%	
Mastitis	6	4.7%	
Leptospirosis	4	3.1%	
Viral Diseases (Other/Non Specified)	4	3.1%	
Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	3	2.4%	
Parasitic Diseases	3	2.4%	
Reproductive/Postpartum Diseases	2	1.6%	
Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE)	2	1.6%	
Metabolic Diseases	2	1.6%	
Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD)	1	0.8%	

Table 4.37.: Category: Meat-Farms. I1: Which livestock diseases cause the most economic loss on your farm?

Question I2 shows that “Early disease detection” is the biggest challenge for many in managing livestock health it dominates with 76%. Small farms also struggle with “Veterinary access” overproportional. In the [Tables 4.38](#) and [4.39](#), the relevant statistics are shown.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Early disease detection	114	76.0%	
Treatment costs	11	7.3%	
Veterinary access	10	6.7%	
Regulatory compliance	2	1.3%	
Record keeping	10	6.7%	
Others (open text response below)	2	1.3%	
No Answer	1	0.7%	

Table 4.38.: Category: Full-dataset. I2: What is your biggest challenge in managing livestock health?

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Early disease detection	30	58.8%	
Treatment costs	6	11.8%	
Veterinary access	8	15.7%	
Regulatory compliance	1	2.0%	
Record keeping	4	7.8%	
Others (open text response below)	2	3.9%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.39.: Category: Small-Farms. I2: What is your biggest challenge in managing livestock health?

Question I2 (Others) the participants were asked if their most significant challenge is something else that was not listed in [Question I2](#). The themed answers are listed in [Table 4.40](#), “Treatment Handling”, “Access to Treatment”, and “Establishment Management” are most noted and will be discussed in depth in [Chapter 5](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Treatment Handling	13	31.0%	
Access to Treatment	11	26.2%	
Establishment Management	8	19.0%	
Health Management	3	7.1%	
Vaccination Handling	3	7.1%	
Sanitation	1	2.4%	
Overall Cost	1	2.4%	
Climate	1	2.4%	
Appropriate Treatment	1	2.4%	

Table 4.40.: Category: Full-dataset. I2 (others): Previous question, if you have another challenge, describe it here

Question I3 concerns early detection by inquiring about the importance of detecting diseases before clinical symptoms appear, yields a less surprising high average value of 4.89¹⁹. This high score is consistent with the answer in [Question I2](#).

4.2.11. Cluster J: Operational Context and Infrastructure

Question J1 asked for the distance to the nearest veterinary clinic. All categories are similarly distributed, as shown in [Table 4.41](#). Small farms are more often located close to the nearest veterinarian clinic, with 43.1% being less than 10km, while large farms are typically farther away, with 41.7% being over 60km, and medium farms are located at 58.3% between 10 and 30km. At the same time, dairy farms never chose the selection “More than 60km”. Driven by the extensive need for land, it is reasonable, as confirmed by two of the piloting experts from [Table 3.2](#), that the distance to the next veterinary clinic correlates with farm size because veterinary clinics are typically located in cities.

¹⁹ Details see in [Appendix B.2](#)

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
Less than 10km	38	25.3%	
10-30km	55	36.7%	
31-60km	27	18.0%	
More than 60km	30	20.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.41.: Category: Full-dataset. J1: How far is the nearest veterinary clinic from your farm?

Question J1a if they usually go to that veterinary clinic is answered by 51% with “Yes”²⁰.

Question J1b if they have their own veterinarians is answered by 63% with “Yes”. Medium farm answered with 88%, small farm (51%), and large (56%) with “Yes”²¹.

Question J2 shows that most farmers have access to the internet, at least via a mobile phone, as shown in the following [Table 4.42](#).

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
High-speed	63	42.0%	
Basic	55	36.7%	
Mobile only	29	19.3%	
Unreliable	0	0.0%	
No internet	3	2.0%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.42.: Category: Full-dataset. J2: Do you have reliable internet connectivity on your farm?

²⁰ Details see in Appendix [B.1](#)

²¹ Details see in Appendix [B.1](#)

Question J3 shows in the full-dataset, there are primarily 1-2 trained personnel who can operate new diagnostic equipment, as shown in [Table 4.43](#). In the category of small farms, it is often selected that “None” employee is capable of operating the new diagnostic equipment with 45.1%. This response does not allow any conclusions related to the number of employees on a farm, and was also not the intention.

Answer	Count	Percent	Bar
None	31	20.7%	
1-2	63	42.0%	
3-5	37	24.7%	
More than 5	19	12.7%	
No Answer	-		

Table 4.43.: Category: Full-dataset. J3: How many trained personnel do you have who could operate new diagnostic equipment?

Question J4 74% feels confident to perform the entire testing process, additionally 23% mentioned with “Depends on conditions” to be able ²².

²² Details see in [B.1](#)

5. Discussion

In this chapter, the results and findings from Chapter 4 are discussed.

No Significance Test The findings will not be tested for significance with a Two-Proportion Z-Test. As discussed in [Section 4.1.2](#), the challenges encountered during helper recruitment include a low response rate, observed both on social media and through direct contact at conferences and institutions. Made it impossible to obtain data from a more heterogeneous area. More details for this limitation are described in [Section 6.4](#).

5.1. RQ1: Current Diagnostic Practices and Gaps in Paraguay

As explained in the [Paragraph: Importance of turnaround time 2.3](#), test result turnaround time for foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) and brucellosis ranges from days to weeks. In [Question A4](#) and [Question A5](#), both diseases are in the top 10 concerns. In [Question I1](#), brucellosis ranks second as the cause of most economic loss on the farm. FMD spreads rapidly to other animals and can occasionally infect humans, while brucellosis spreads more slowly but is significantly zoonotic. Longer turnaround times increase the severity of outbreaks for both diseases. [Francis \(2022\)](#) identifies slow result return time as the biggest diagnostic challenge in Sub-Saharan Africa, a comparable developing region, and emphasises point-of-care (POC) testing as a solution.

“Early disease detection” is in [Question I2](#) selected as the biggest challenge. In [Question E4](#) the immediate availability of test results is rated as very important. Farmers generally consult their own veterinarian. There is no tendency if they visit this professional or get a visit to their farm from them ([Question J1a](#), [J1b](#)).

The blood samples must be processed in Veterinary clinics or central laboratories, yet [Question J1](#) indicates that large farms are often located far from these facilities. Transport is time-intensive, primarily due to poor roads, which further delay results.

Farm Size and Farm Type Conditions in Paraguay The [Rural Association of Paraguay](#) (2019, p. 5) reports that 89% of herds contain fewer than 100 cattle, and herds raised for meat comprise 90% of farms in Paraguay.

Paraguay Vaccine Practice Although vaccinations exist for FMD and Brucellosis, and national campaigns are being carried out ([Valor Agro, 2025](#)), several independent veterinarians confirm that outbreaks persist, mentioning this as a problem, sometimes due to hygiene lapses among large and medium farms. Farms with ≥ 100 cattle are responsible for administering their own vaccinations, which could support this effect. Brucellosis is in a lower rank in small farms concerns, as shown in [Table 4.5](#), where their herd size was consistently below 100 due to the quantization.

Paraguay Diagnostic Practice Seasonal testing was the option selected most often in [Question A3](#). [Question B1](#) shows that 71% of respondents performed blood tests to optimise herd health. [Question C1](#) shows that “Access-Related Barriers” and “Process/Procedural Barriers” are two of the top three reasons for not performing tests.

RQ 1:

Gaps could be closed by removing access barriers and streamlining procedures that currently impede testing.

5.2. RQ2: Priority Diseases Benefit from POC and LoAD Technology Potential

In addition to FMD and brucellosis, which were evaluated in [Section 5.1](#), mastitis also appears in the top ranks in disease-related questions and is highly related to dairy farms see [Section 4.8](#). Piroplasmosis and Anaplasmosis are also present, but to a lesser extent. Piroplasmosis is also among the top three, with the highest

economic losses. [Question B2](#) shows a clear trend to perform a blood test by themselves. Different veterinary experts have confirmed that this is common, either due to spending less money or a lack of access.

In [Question D4](#), 92% answered that they would reduce antibiotic use if a simple test were available. [Question D4](#) indicates that “Treatment Optimization”, “Economic Efficiency” and “Antibiotic resistance” are main driver for this use. The willingness to reduce antibiotic use, when simple tests are available, promises greater support for the one-health approach to reduce antibiotic resistance, as explained in [Section 2.1.1](#). [Question E3](#) shows with 94% “Yes” response that a provided test accuracy of 90% will be accepted. More important is that the test is immediately available, with an average score of 4.73 on a scale from 1 to 5, as presented in [Question E4](#). Lab-on-a-Disc is not a familiar term, as mentioned in [Question H5](#). The author suspects that it could be even lower, and some only heard about it in conversations with interviewers prior to the survey. Although the interviewers were trained not to use these terms.

Disease with Potential for LoAD As discussed in [Section 2.4.3](#), LAMP, PCR, ELISA, and FLISA are implemented with LoAD. In [Table 5.1](#), the top-mentioned diseases are listed and rated as excellent or good candidates for the LoAD technology. Other diseases that are good candidates for LoAD but are not highly ranked in disease-related questions will not be listed in [Table 5.1](#).

Disease	Top concern	Top economic loss	Candidates POC/LoaD	Reference
Brucellosis	Top 3	Top 3	Excellent	(Manassis et al., 2022, pp. 16-17)
Mastitis	Top 3	Top 3	Excellent	(Manassis et al., 2022, pp. 18-24) (Phiphattanaphiphop et al., 2023)
FMD	Top 10	Out of Top 10	Excellent	(Manassis et al., 2022, pp. 18-24)
Anaplasmosis	Top 3	Top 3	Good (showing potential)	Sutipatanasomboon et al. (2024)
Piroplasmosis	Top 3	Top 3	Weak	no evidence found

Table 5.1.: Candidates for LoaD Technology

RQ 2:

Brucellosis, FMD, and Mastitis (especially for dairy farms) are great candidates for entering the market in Paraguay

5.3. RQ3: Early Adopter Stakeholder Groups

Farmers most often consult veterinarians for decisions related to livestock health. Large farms show the most outstanding willingness to try a new technology when it is recommended by a trusted veterinarian (Question F1, F5). Associations and cooperatives are effective outreach channels because 55% of farmers belong to one, and they also prefer face-to-face meetings, see Question F2 and F3.

Trust increases when cooperatives operate the testing device, particularly for dairy and medium farms (Question F4). More than 50% of respondents learn about new technologies through professional advisors and peer networks. Large farms require clear evidence of effectiveness before adoption and report high digital familiarity (Question H1, H2, H3). Table 4.34 in Question H4 shows that peer testimonials motivate large farms to try new technologies more than financial incentives. Ohashi

et al. (2024) highlights that technology adoption depends on multiple resources and stages. Because large farms possess more resources and show the most willingness to invest a longer time in learning a new diagnostic regarding [Question C4](#), they are identified as the most likely early adopters.

How to Address Large Farms as Stakeholders for Early Adoption [Question H5](#) shows that LoaD remains unfamiliar to most stakeholders. To make the technology more widely known, veterinarians, as representatives of professional advisors, can collaborate among cooperatives and other associations, serving as a platform for peer networks and providing the most effective pathway to reach large farms. Face-to-face meetings are the preferred channel. Test demonstrations shall prove the device's effectiveness and include peer testimonials.

RQ 3:

Face-to-face meetings are the preferred channel to reach large farms as early adopters.

5.4. RQ4: Cultural Factors and Trust in Technology Adoption

Simple and cost-effective testing will be used by 95% if the method is available ([Question C2](#)). [Question C2a](#) shows the crucial factors that a test will be used:

- improvement for health management
- bringing economic benefits
- supports practical implementation

On the other hand, cost, complexity, and reliability are the biggest concerns ([Question C3](#)). A general skeptical culture related to trust, could explain why 88% agree, and an additional 9%, depending on the condition, that trust increases with purchasing a tested, certified cattle. It mainly increases confidence in preventing the spread. [Question E1](#) and [E1a](#) provide more details. Veterinarians, associations, and cooperatives increase trust as mentioned in previous [Section 5.3](#). These trust relationships align with findings from [Grace et al. \(2008\)](#).

Build a Trustful Channel Trust is crucial in business, especially in a developing country with additional challenging conditions, as explained in [Paraguayan market environment, in Section 1.1.3](#). To reach adoption-willing farmers, the different farm categories should be targeted at the channel where this group is familiar and trusts. For large farms, this would be done by a veterinarian through face-to-face meetings.

RQ 4:

The different farm categories need to be targeted with channels where this group is familiar and trusts.

5.5. RQ5: Economically Viable Business Models and Pricing

Considering statistics in [Question D1](#), the prices should be targeted in the range of 25th percentile (P25) and the 75th percentile (P75). [Table 5.2](#) provides an overview in Paraguayan currency, Guaraníes, and equivalent US Dollar prices applicable on September 2025.

Category	25th percentile (P25)		75th percentile (P75)	
	Guaraníes	USD	Guaraníes	USD
Individual test	10 000	1.4	21 250	3.0
Complete testing package	48 500	6.7	150 000	21.0

Table 5.2.: Stakeholder expected costs of diagnostic testing per cattle (excluding small farms (P75))

[Section 2.4.4](#) shows that higher costs per test for LoAD in comparison to automated laboratory tests increase the POC testing costs. The authors in [St John and Price \(2013, pp. 1-2\)](#) also mention the higher costs for POC tests, but recognize that the price is partially higher due to fewer scaling effects and lower volume compared to automated laboratories. Volume-based pricing models, attractive for large farms and cooperatives, are a method to counter this effect.

Limited Finance and Purchase POC Devices In [Eloit \(2019\)](#), the importance of veterinary services and their crucial role in global health security is mentioned. It states that one of the two main problems is that investment in livestock accounts for only 4.5% of development funding for agriculture. At the same time, 40% of agriculture Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is related to livestock in developing countries. This results in a lack of investment and funding for diagnostic equipment.

The answers in the survey support this advocacy report ([Eloit, 2019](#)). [Question D2](#), highlighting the limited financial resources, 66% would spend a maximum of 1% of their annual turnover on diagnostic equipment. On the other hand, in [Question D3](#), a device purchase dominates, accounting for 58%. This constraint, low financial flexibility but more trust in the purchase, presents a challenging situation in finding a pricing model that fits.

5.5.1. Business Model and Pricing Strategy

Price Downsizing Options With a suitable physical layout on the disc, the same test can be provided several times on the same disc. That makes sense for mass testing to prevent the spread of diseases like FMD and brucellosis, and it reduces the price per test. Implementing different common disease test kit on the same test disc would be another opportunity to reduce the Load test prices.

Pricing Strategy Volume-based pricing models are a method to reduce the price. Large farms, with their vast herds, are a good target group and are also identified as early adopter candidates.

Business Model A [Question E2](#) represents the willingness to pay a higher price for livestock that has certified test results. That opens a business model to offer certifications during cattle transfers, especially at the fairs, which provide a substantial part of the cattle market. In [Avalos et al. \(2022\)](#), the cattle exchange over these markets is called “super-spreading events ([Avalos et al., 2022](#))”. Furthermore, it highlights these hubs as a crucial factor in the spread of diseases, mainly for FMD and brucellosis. The article [Avalos et al. \(2025\)](#) also supports this finding.

A service on these markets that allows cattle to be tested on site during the purchase process can provide an additional option for market entry.

Business Model B Based on participant feedback that favors device ownership, but considering their limited financial resources, implementing a pricing strategy that bundles the POC device at no cost, while slightly increasing test fees, could create a more attractive offering.

RQ 5:

A promising strategy imposes itself: Firstly, bringing the test price down. Further implement a volume-based pricing strategy and provide the devices.

5.6. RQ6: Implementation Requirements (Training, Support, Infrastructure)

Related to [Question E5](#), the fact that 83% want to share anonymized test results with search institutions to improve livestock health will be an essential factor to enhance training and support programs.

Training Because [Question B2](#) and [D5](#) show a clear trend that farmers prefer to perform the test by themselves, an easy device is elementary, and also in [Question B3](#) on the first rank. This finding is consistent with the research by [Michael et al. \(2016, pp. 4,10\)](#), which emphasizes the importance of simple user interfaces and training with low technical barriers.

To successfully enter the market and reach early adopters, the training should focus on performing the test on the farm by farmers or their employees. In [Section 5.3](#), the author discussed that large farms show more willingness for training. In [Question J3](#), dairy farms and large farms (good candidates for early adopters) selected one or more available personnel who could be trained. At the same time, 74% feel confident in performing the entire testing process. Additionally, 23% mentioned with “Depends on conditions” ([Question J4](#)). The training should be conducted on-site at farms belonging to cooperatives or similar peer associations, involving local veterinarians who explain and perform the tests with the trainees. Training that shares experience will foster confidence and produce new advocates among farmers. A good starting point is to utilize Paraguay’s strong and established cooperative and association structure, which advocates for its members in organizing and politics. Also, it supports their memberships and others with access to new technology and

training, as explained in [IDH Transforming Markets \(2017\)](#); [Suárez Beltrán \(2024\)](#); [van der Bijl et al. \(2016\)](#).

Support The high average value of 4.46 on a scale from 1 to 5 to feel comfortable using digital technologies in farming operations ([Question H3](#)), opens the door for digital support to support POC testing by farmers themselves. Using artificial intelligence (AI) is an additional supporting technology. An additional support for regulating knowledge transfer to address the lack of information, pointed out in [Question G1](#), is an opportunity to increase new technology acceptance and win adopters.

With an average scale of over 4, for most farmers it is important that diagnostic technologies complies with national livestock regulations shown in [Question G2](#). To consider this need, the digital support as well as local support through personal meetings shall comply with national regulations.

Infrastructure To utilize the digital support proposed in the previous paragraph, internet connectivity is essential. [Question J2](#) indicates that on most farms, internet is at least over mobile phone available. At this point, some remarks are necessary:

- The survey was performed in a few areas in Paraguay, and internet connectivity could be different in other areas
- Power loss is common in Paraguay and occurs weekly. In warm months, it can increase to daily due to the high energy consumption of air conditioner. That sometimes affects the internet connectivity. Power loss in developing countries and its effect on ePOCT is discussed in [Michael et al. \(2016, p. 4\)](#)
- The data bandwidth can be very low for the 19.3% who selected internet access over mobile phone, see [Table 4.42](#)

With these limitations, a POC device and its supporting mobile phone application should be able to temporarily function without internet connectivity, at least with basic functionalities. The POC device should be able to bridge at least a few hours of power loss with a battery to perform the test. There could be a solution to interpret the result later by scanning the QR code or RFID chip on the disc and an offline image on the mobile phone from the test result when internet connectivity is back. Cattle with chipped or other registered identification must be traced to the test QR code or test RFID chip. A national tracability system in Paraguay

has been implemented since 2004, which tracks origin and movement, as shown in [Ramirez Pastore and West \(2019\)](#).

RQ 6:

Simple on-site training, introduced by local veterinarians, enables farmers to perform testing independently. A digital application and personal support will be provided to them after training, so that they do not feel alone, gain confidence with the latest technology, and can advocate the new methodical approach.

6. Conclusions

This chapter presents conclusions and insights into the potential for Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) technology to enter Paraguay's cattle sector, offering a framework applicable to developing countries in South America. In the previous [Chapter 5](#), all six research questions are addressed and the author provides recommendations for stakeholders considering point-of-care diagnostic implementations and LoaD test kit development for diseases with the most concerns or the most economic loss.

6.1. Expansion to Other Developing Countries

Applicability Validation To test whether the findings from Paraguay apply to other developing countries, a thorough comparison is recommended in advance, at least through preliminary studies.

The following checklist is provided as a framework:

- Economical (cost sensitivity)
- Climatic conditions
- Farm types characteristics
- National vaccination programs
- Environment and infrastructure (road condition, internet connection)
- Centralized laboratory access
- Cultural conditions (adoption openness, trusted stakeholders, willingness to perform the test by themselves)

One Health Integration Potential The high willingness to reduce antibiotic use (92%) and the often mentioned connection to antibiotic resistance by farmers in the open questions promise success with financial support for a national campaign. Learning from these implementations can be applied to other large meat-producing

countries with similar conditions, such as Brazil and Argentina. Sharing anonymized test results with search institutions to improve livestock health by 83% indicates a potential for integrated programs that support a one-health approach, providing benefits for both animal and human health.

6.2. Summary of Key Findings

Market Potential for Testing Expansion While the current state of research shows the immense economic losses related to diseases in the cattle sector (Kyr-iazakis et al., 2024; Strydom et al., 2023) and the actual and future rising challenges with antibiotic resistance, the study in Paraguay by questioning the most involved stakeholders, farmers and veterinarians, confirms the potential for more testing and inherent improvements. 61.3% tests only seasonally or less their livestock for health monitoring (Table 4.3).

Point-of-Care Testing Potential The survey confirmed findings from research in other developing countries that the access-related barriers are the main reason for not performing the test (Table 4.12). The willingness to perform tests on the farm and conduct them independently is a remarkable potential for POC testing and user-friendly test kit implementation, particularly with a simple Lab-on-a-Disk (LoaD) test kit.

Disease Candidates LoaD Diseases that frequently appear and have a significant impact on animal and human well-being are the primary candidates to address by developing test kits. In the survey, the three diseases Brucellosis, Mastitis, and FMD were identified, and the suitability for POC devices is listed in (Table 5.1).

Early Adopter Stakeholder Group In Section 5.3, it is explained why large farms are the ideal stakeholder group for early adopters.

Pricing and Business Models Section 5.5 shows the pricing and business model by implementing a volume-based pricing strategy and providing the devices. Price

ranges for a single individual test and a complete testing package are also evaluated. The main implementation requirements discussed in [Section 5.6](#) are:

- Simple training to allow farmers to perform testing by themselves
- Support by a digital application and personal support in place

6.3. Research Contribution

Knowledge Contribution The research provides understanding for technology adoption in Paraguay and how it can expand to other developing countries, supporting a small piece to close the gap in existing POCT research, which focuses primarily on human healthcare applications to support the one-health approach to handle the antibiotics resistance challenge together with both animal and human health.

Methodological Contribution The methodological chapter and the adaptations in results and findings demonstrate how to implement research in English in a bilingual, developing country with a limited number of English speakers. Building an expert group comprising locals and foreigners with several years of experience living in the target country, all from different professions, was a crucial strategic decision to gather cultural and technical insights.

Practical Contributions Multiple stakeholders can benefit from the research and the gathered dataset. Regulatory to identify regulatory gaps. Live science industry for price targeting and development aims. Veterinary medicine and government for potential local improvements in Paraguay. Non-profit organization to target developing programs.

6.4. Limitations

Geographic Coverage Limitations The main reason that findings can not be tested for significance with a Two-Proportion Z-Test is that the dataset focuses on a few provinces in Paraguay, which have varying weather and climate conditions due to their geographical location. It does not fully represent the country as a whole

and may influence the rankings of diseases. Different infrastructure levels are another unknown influencing factor that makes conclusions for many other questions with mathematical significance obsolete.

No Load Validation The research is not understandable as a technological Load validation.

Time Dependency Business-related findings represent the current status and can be influenced by economic changes in Paraguay, climatic changes, and technological disruptions in POC testing.

Methodological Limitations There is no control over the influence of the interviewer on participants and other biases without the use of a control group or several studies that will be compared in a meta-study.

6.5. Stakeholder Recommendations

For Technology Developers For technology developers, the three primary candidates for developing test kits are the three diseases: Brucellosis, Mastitis, and FMD, one of the key findings, as shown in [Section 5.2](#). While Mastitis targets dairy farms, Brucellosis and FMD are tested on a mass scale, especially for large farms, to prevent spread and economic loss. The test kit should be easy to use, and the test results should be easy to interpret. In the cost-sensitive market, the price for a single test ranges from 1.4 USD to 3 USD, and for a complete testing package, it ranges from 6.7 USD to 21 USD. [Table 5.2](#) lists the price ranges. In [Section 5.1](#), the biggest challenges in a developing country are summarized. Given the conditions in Paraguay and the similarities to other developing countries, robust POC/ePOC devices are necessary to support the test kits adequately.

For Implementation Organizations The implementation organization should choose its channels carefully to respect the preferences of its targeted farmer category. For large farms, this would be veterinarians. Cooperative-based implementation should

be considered because more than 50% of respondents are members of a cooperative or similar association and trust devices more if they are provided by one of these.

For Policymakers and Regulators The lack of regulation is highlighted in [Section 2.4.4](#). The author suggests that policymakers and regulators should establish useful and practical regulatory frameworks for veterinary point-of-care testing. Involving farmers and device makers as stakeholders to develop suitable regulations that enhance security for both animals and humans, while mitigating business risks and uncertainty, could attract this enormous business sector for innovative technologies.

For Development Organizations Development organizations, such as non-profit organizations, foundations, and other entities, should note the high willingness of over 90% to reduce antibiotic use, as seen in [Question D4](#).

By providing equipment and tests to farmers at an affordable price range without access barriers, this initiative offers a significant lever to combat antibiotic resistance. The funding models should consider that two-thirds have an annual turnover capacity of less than 1% to invest in diagnostic equipment, shown in [Table 4.19](#). Innovative financing approaches such as cooperative-based ownership, pay-per-test models for small farms, and equipment sharing programs.

To reach the farmers, different target groups need adapted strategies. To get the early adopter group of large farms is more likely through veterinarians. On the other hand, cooperatives would be a high-potential channel for the target group of dairy farms. Other factors related to the test device and the tests expected from the survey participants are listed in several tables and in [Section 5.4](#).

6.6. Future Research Directions

Validation and Expanding Studies Recommendations for the future include focusing on field validation of LoaD technology with stakeholders from the early adopter group, specifically large farms. To gather insight into device performance, user experience, and economic outcomes. The effectiveness of different implementation strategies is another field to research. Comparing LoaD technology with alternative diagnostic approaches, including other POC technologies.

Framework Test By using the provided framework in [Section 6.1](#) for another developing country, its applicability and robustness can be tested.

Establishment of Effective Training Future research established as a best practice project should test a training structure to reach farmers, involve veterinarians, cooperatives, and other relevant associations.

Multi-Disease Testing Future research should observe the potential for multi-disease on a disc. An additional approach involves performing several test assays on the same disease on the same discs to monitor herds and prevent the spread, or to offer it as a service on cattle markets. That allows for a more accurate estimation of the potential to decrease the price per test kit.

Policy and Regulatory Research By researching the regulatory gaps for Point-of-Care testing in the leading meat-producing countries, it is possible to provide a framework and guidelines to responsible government stakeholders to reduce uncertainties for farmers and test and device-providing companies. Additionally, it would eliminate risks associated with non-compliance with future regulations that may be introduced.

6.7. Final Conclusion

While challenges exist, including cost sensitivity, regulatory gaps, and infrastructure limitations, as well as the fact that the author did not find a test kit in the expected price range.

This research demonstrates the significant potential of LoAD to help close testing gaps in Paraguay's cattle sector, preventing the spread of diseases like FMD and brucellosis, and decreasing economic losses by reducing Mastitis. The author identified the early adopter target group and uncovered the high willingness to reduce antibiotic use (92%) if a simple test process with dismantled access barriers is provided. The provided framework for other developing countries supports and accelerates further research under similar conditions. LoAD technology is a valuable tool in the one-health strategy to mitigate global antibiotic and antimicrobial resistance.

They found a strict trust relationship between farmers and veterinarians as advisors, and the role of cooperative structures provides clear pathways for successful implementation.

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A. Questionnaire

In English

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question and Objective
Cluster A: Farm Profile and Operations		
A1. How many animals do you own?	Number / I am a veterinarian	RQ1, Objective 1: Basic farm profiling for understanding diagnostic practices and needs
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
A2. What type of livestock do you have?	Type / I am a veterinarian	RQ1, Objective 1: Identifies livestock types to assess specific diagnostic requirements
A3. How often do you currently test your livestock for health monitoring?	Categorical: Daily / Weekly / Monthly / Seasonally / Annually / Never	RQ1, Objective 1: Maps current diagnostic frequency to identify testing gaps
A4. What specific livestock diseases are you most concerned about on your farm?	Several words	RQ1, RQ2, Objective 1: Identifies priority diseases for POC diagnostic needs
A5. Besides this disease in the previous question, what other disease or diseases do you concern most?	Several words	RQ1, RQ2, Objective 1: Expands disease priority list for comprehensive diagnostic assessment
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
Cluster B: Current Practices and Experience		
B1. Have you previously conducted blood tests to systematically optimize your herd's health?	Yes / No	RQ1, Objective 1: Assesses current diagnostic experience and practices
B2. Would you like to do a blood test by yourself on a farm and get the result faster than send it to the laboratory?	Yes / No / Depends on conditions	RQ2, RQ6, Objective 1: Evaluates POC testing preference and implementation needs
B3. What requirements would this testing method need to fulfill for you to use it? (e.g., accuracy, speed, ease of use, price, etc.)	several words	RQ1, RQ6, Objective 1: Identifies technical requirements for LoAD implementation
Cluster C: Barriers and Adoption Potential		
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
C1. If you have not used such blood tests or diagnostics, what were the main reasons or obstacles? (e.g., cost, complexity, lack of information, lack of access, etc.)	several words	RQ1, Objective 2: Identifies barriers to current diagnostic adoption
C2. If a simple and cost-effective testing method were available, would you consider using it?	Yes / No	RQ4, Objective 2: Assesses adoption potential for new diagnostic technologies
C2a. What is the reason of using or do not using it?	Open text response	RQ4, Objective 2: Explores deeper reasons for technology adoption decisions
C3. What is your primary concern about adopting new diagnostic technologies?	Categorical: Cost / Complexity / Reliability / Training requirements / Regulatory compliance / Other	RQ4, Objective 2: Categorizes main barriers to technology adoption
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
C4. How many hours of training would you be willing to invest in learning a new diagnostic test?	Categorical: 0-5 hours / 6-10 hours / 11-20 hours / 21-40 hours / above 40 hours	RQ3, RQ6, Objective 3: Assesses training capacity for implementation framework
Cluster D: Economic Considerations and Preferences		
D1. What would be an acceptable price for such a test for common economically significant livestock diseases you mentioned above:	D1a and D1b	RQ5, Objective 3: Determines pricing thresholds for business model development
D1a. Price per individual test:	number	RQ5, Objective 3: Specific pricing data for per-test business model
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
D1b. Price for a complete testing package per cattle:	number	RQ5, Objective 3: Package pricing data for comprehensive diagnostic strategy
D2. What is the maximum you would invest in diagnostic equipment related to your annual turnover?	Categorical: 0-0.5% / 0.5-1% / 1-2%/ 2-5%/ over 5% of the annual turnover / I do not know/I do not measure	RQ5, Objective 3: Investment capacity assessment for equipment business models
D3. Would you prefer to purchase diagnostic equipment outright or pay per test?	Categorical: Purchase / Pay-per-test / Subscription model / Lease / Other	RQ5, Objective 3: Business model preference for sustainable implementation
D4. Would you reduce antibiotic use if a simple test could determine the necessity and type of medication?	Yes / No	RQ2, Objective 1: Evaluates AMR reduction potential through targeted diagnostics
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
D4a. What is the reason of reduce or do not reduce it?	Open text response	RQ2, Objective 1: Understanding motivations for responsible antibiotic use
D5. As a farmer, would you prefer to operate a Point-of-Care (POC) test yourself or use an external service that isn't available around the clock?	Categorical: self / service	RQ6, Objective 3: Service delivery model preference for implementation framework
Cluster E: Trust, Value, and Decision-Making		
E1. Would your trust in purchasing livestock increase if the animal came with certified test results?	Yes / No / Depends on conditions	RQ4, Objective 2: Assesses trust factors in technology adoption
E1a. What is the reason of increase trust or why it does not increase your trust, or what would be the condition which it depends?	Open text response /no answer	RQ4, Objective 2: Explores conditions affecting trust in diagnostic technology
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
E2. Would you be willing to pay a higher price for livestock that has certified test results?	Yes / No	RQ5, Objective 3: Value proposition assessment for trading platform pricing strategies
E3. If a test provides 90% accuracy, would you still consider it beneficial and use it?	Yes / No	RQ2, Objective 1: Acceptable performance thresholds for Load diagnostics
E4. How important is it that test results are immediately available on-site versus sent to a laboratory?	Scale 1-5	RQ1, RQ2, Objective 1: Importance of POC versus centralized testing
E5. Would you share anonymized test results with research institutions if it helped improve livestock health in your region?	Yes / No / Depends on conditions	RQ5, RQ6, Objective 3: Data sharing willingness for technology development and improvement
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
Cluster F: Information Sources and Communication Channels		
F1. Who do you consult most when making decisions about livestock health management?	Categorical: Veterinarian / Fellow farmers / Government extension agent / Online resources / Family members / Other	RQ3, RQ4, Objective 2: Identifies key stakeholders and decision-making networks
F2. What is your preferred method of receiving information about new agricultural technologies?	Categorical: Face-to-face meetings / Phone calls / Text messages / Email / Social media / Printed materials / Radio / Television	RQ3, Objective 3: Communication channels for technology transfer and training
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
F3. Do you belong to any farmer associations or cooperatives?	Yes / No	RQ3, Objective 2: Identifies enabling community structures for adoption
F4. Would your trust be strengthened if a testing device were operated through the cooperative?	Yes / No	RQ3, RQ4, Objective 2: Cooperative structures as trust enablers
F5. How likely are you to try a new technology if recommended by a trusted veterinarian?	Scale 1-5	RQ3, RQ4, Objective 2: Influence of trusted advisors on adoption decisions
Cluster G: Regulatory and Compliance Awareness		
G1. Are you familiar with current regulations regarding livestock health testing in your country?	Scale 1-5 / no answer	RQ6, Objective 3: Regulatory awareness for compliance framework development and training
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
G2. How important is it that diagnostic technologies comply with national livestock regulations?	Scale 1-5 / no answer	RQ6, Objective 3: Regulatory compliance importance for implementation framework
Cluster H: Innovation Adoption Profile		
H1. How do you typically learn about the existence of new agricultural technologies?	Open text response	RQ3, Objective 2: Technology awareness channels for early adopter identification
H2. What is the most important factor when deciding to adopt a new technology?	Categorical: Proven effectiveness / Cost-benefit ratio / Ease of use / Peer recommendations / Regulatory approval / No experience	RQ3, Objective 2: Key adoption decision factors for stakeholder profiling
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
H3. How comfortable are you with using digital technologies in your farming operations?	Scale 1-5	RQ3, RQ6, Objective 2: Digital readiness assessment for early adopter identification
H4. What would motivate you to be among the first to try a new livestock diagnostic technology?	Categorical: Financial incentives / Free trial period / Training support / Peer testimonials / Scientific evidence	RQ3, Objective 2: Early adoption motivators for stakeholder targeting
H5. Have you heard of Lab-on-a-Disc (LoaD) diagnostic technology?	Yes / No	RQ2, RQ3, Objective 1: LoaD technology awareness assessment
Cluster I: Livestock Health Priorities and Disease Concerns		
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
I1. Which livestock diseases cause the most economic loss on your farm?	several words	RQ1, RQ2, Objective 1: Economic impact prioritization for POC diagnostic targeting
I2. What is your biggest challenge in managing livestock health?	Categorical: Early disease detection / Treatment costs / Veterinary access / Regulatory compliance / Record keeping / Others (open text response)	RQ1, Objective 1: Key health management challenges identification
I3. How important is it to detect diseases before clinical symptoms appear?	Scale 1-5	RQ5, Objective 3: Early detection importance for systematically testing
Cluster J: Operational Context and Infrastructure		
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
J1. How far is the nearest veterinary clinic from your farm?	Categorical: Less than 10km / 10-30km / 31-60km / More than 60km	RQ1, RQ6, Objective 1: Infrastructure constraints affecting diagnostic access
J1a. Do you usually go to that veterinary clinic?	Yes / No	RQ1, Objective 1: Current veterinary service utilization patterns
J1b. Do you have your own veterinarians?	Yes / No	RQ1, Objective 1: Veterinary dependencies and capabilities
J2. Do you have reliable internet connectivity on your farm?	Categorical: High-speed / Basic / Mobile only / Unreliable / No internet	RQ6, Objective 3: Infrastructure requirements for digital diagnostic implementation
Continued on next page		

Table A.2 – continued from previous page

Question	Answer structure	Reason link to research question
J3. How many trained personnel do you have who could operate new diagnostic equipment?	Categorical: None / 1-2 / 3-5 / More than 5	RQ6, Objective 3: Human resource capacity for technology implementation
J4. Could you independently perform the entire testing process, from taking a blood sample from a cow to evaluating the result with an application on a mobile phone?	Yes / No / Depends on conditions	RQ6, Objective 3: Self-testing capability assessment for implementation framework

Spanish Printed Version The following Spanish survey shows the handout for participants who preferred a paper version.

Evaluación del potencial de las plataformas microfluídicas centrífugas para la detección de enfermedades del ganado

Su experiencia puede marcar el futuro de la actividad ganadera en Paraguay.

Gracias por tomarse el tiempo de considerar este cuestionario dirigido por Felipe para su Investigación para la Universidad de Cumbria, una respetada Universidad del Reino Unido.

Como productor ganadero o veterinario, sus opiniones son esenciales para comprender los problemas de salud que afectan al ganado en Paraguay. Las enfermedades no sólo afectan a los animales, sino también a la productividad y los ingresos de las familias rurales.

Al compartir su experiencia, está contribuyendo directamente a soluciones prácticas, asequibles y adaptadas a nuestras necesidades locales. Esta investigación ayudará a llevar a Paraguay recursos, apoyo técnico y estrategias eficaces para proteger el medio ambiente, mejorar el bienestar animal y fortalecer nuestras comunidades.

Tu voz importa, y cada respuesta cuenta. Su participación realmente marca la diferencia.
¡Gracias por formar parte de esta iniciativa!

Instrucciones: Marque las casillas correspondientes con una “X” y complete las líneas donde se solicite. No cambie el contenido ni el orden de las preguntas.

Perfil de la estancia y operaciones

1. ¿Cuántos animales posee?

Yo soy veterinario (escriba aquí una “X” si corresponde)

2. ¿Qué tipo de ganado tiene?

Yo soy veterinario (escriba aquí una “X” si corresponde)

3. ¿Con qué frecuencia realiza actualmente pruebas de control sanitario a su ganado?
(Elige solo una respuesta)

Diariamente Semanalmente Mensualmente Estacionalmente
 Anualmente Nunca

4. ¿Qué enfermedades específicas del ganado le preocupan más en su estancia?
(no es necesario rellenar todos los campos)

_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____

5. Además de la enfermedad mencionada en la pregunta anterior, ¿qué otra enfermedad o enfermedades le preocupan más?
(no es necesario rellenar todos los campos)

_____	_____
_____	_____

Prácticas actuales y experiencia

6. ¿Ha realizado anteriormente análisis de sangre para optimizar sistemáticamente la salud de su ganado?

Sí No

7. ¿Le gustaría hacer un análisis de sangre usted mismo en la estancia y obtener el resultado más rápidamente que enviarlo al laboratorio?

Sí No Según las condiciones

8. ¿Qué requisitos tendría que cumplir este método de análisis para que usted lo utilizara? (p. ej. precisión, rapidez, facilidad de uso, precio)
no es necesario rellenar todos los campos

_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____

Obstáculos y potencial de aceptación

9. Si no ha utilizado estos análisis de sangre o diagnósticos, ¿cuáles han sido las principales razones u obstáculos?
(p. ej. coste, complejidad, falta de información, acceso)
no es necesario rellenar todos los campos

10. Si existiera un método de análisis sencillo y económico, ¿consideraría la posibilidad de utilizarlo?

Sí No

11. ¿Cuál es la razón para utilizarlo o no? (en relación con la pregunta anterior)

12. ¿Cuál es su principal preocupación respecto a la incorporación de nuevas tecnologías de diagnóstico? (Elige solo una respuesta)

Coste Complejidad Fiabilidad Requisitos de formación
 Cumplimiento de la normativa Otros

13. ¿Cuántas horas de formación estaría dispuesto a invertir en aprender una nueva prueba diagnóstica? (Elige solo una respuesta)

0-5 horas 6-10 horas 11-20 horas 21-40 horas Más de 40 horas

Consideraciones económicas y preferencias

14. ¿Cuál sería un precio razonable para una prueba diagnóstica que detecte las principales enfermedades(s) del ganado, de acuerdo a las patologías mencionadas anteriormente?

Precio por prueba individual: _____

Precio de un paquete completo de pruebas por ganado: _____

15. ¿Cuál es el máximo que invertiría en equipos de diagnóstico en relación con su volumen de negocios anual? (Elige solo una respuesta)

- 0-0,5% de la facturación anual 0,5-1% de la facturación anual
 1-2% de la facturación anual 2-5% de la facturación anual
 Más de 5% de la facturación anual No lo sé/No mido

16. ¿Preferiría adquirir el equipo de diagnóstico en su totalidad o pagar por cada prueba? (Elige solo una respuesta)

- Compra Pago por prueba Modelo de suscripción Alquiler Otros

17. ¿Reduciría el uso de antibióticos si una simple prueba pudiera determinar la necesidad y el tipo de medicación?

- Sí No

18. ¿Cuál es la razón para reducirlo o no reducirlo? (en relación con la pregunta anterior)

19. Como ganadero, ¿preferiría realizar usted mismo una prueba como un punto de atención (POC por sus siglas en inglés) o recurrir a un servicio externo que no esté disponible las 24 horas del día?

- Yo mismo Servicio externo

Confianza, valor y toma de decisiones

20. ¿Aumentaría su confianza a la hora de comprar ganado si el animal viniera con resultados certificados de sus pruebas?

- Sí No Según las condiciones

21. ¿Cuál es la razón de que aumente su confianza o por qué no aumentaría, o cuál sería la condición de la que depende?

(en relación con la pregunta anterior (sin respuesta también está bien))

22. ¿Estaría dispuesto a pagar un precio más alto por el ganado con resultados certificados?
- Sí No
23. Si una prueba ofrece una precisión del 90 %, ¿seguiría considerándola beneficiosa y la utilizaría?
- Sí No
24. ¿Qué importancia tiene que los resultados de las pruebas estén disponibles inmediatamente in situ en lugar de enviarse a un laboratorio?
- 1 (no importante) 2 3 4 5 (muy importante)
25. ¿Compartiría los resultados anónimos de las pruebas con instituciones de investigación si ello ayudara a mejorar la salud del ganado en su región?
- Sí No Según las condiciones

Fuentes de información y canales de comunicación

26. ¿A quién consulta más a la hora de tomar decisiones sobre la gestión de la salud ganadera? (Elige solo una respuesta)
- Veterinario Compañeros ganaderos
 Agente de extensión gubernamental Recursos en línea Familiares Otro
27. ¿Cuál es su método preferido para recibir información sobre nuevas tecnologías agro ganaderas? (Elige solo una respuesta)
- Reuniones presenciales Llamadas telefónicas Mensajes de texto
 Correo electrónico Redes sociales Material impreso Radio Televisión
28. ¿Pertenece a alguna asociación o cooperativa agro ganadera?
- Sí No
29. ¿Su grado de confianza se vería incrementado si un dispositivo de prueba funcionara a través de la cooperativa?
- Sí No
30. ¿Qué probabilidad hay de que usted pruebe una nueva tecnología si se la recomienda un veterinario de confianza?
- 1 (nada probable) 2 3 4 5 (muy probable)

Conocimiento de la normativa y su cumplimiento

31. ¿Conoce la normativa vigente en su país en materia de pruebas de salud ganadera?
- 1 (no conoce) 2 3 4 5 (muy conoce) Sin respuesta
32. ¿Hasta qué punto es importante que las tecnologías de diagnóstico cumplan la normativa ganadera nacional?
- 1 (no importante) 2 3 4 5 (muy importante) Sin respuesta

Perfil de aceptación de la innovación

33. ¿Cómo suele enterarse de la existencia de nuevas tecnologías agro ganaderas?
- _____
- _____
- _____
34. ¿Cuál es el factor más importante a la hora de decidir adoptar una nueva tecnología? (Elige solo una respuesta)
- Eficacia comprobada Relación coste–beneficio Facilidad de uso
 Recomendaciones de expertos Aprobación reglamentaria Sin experiencia
35. ¿Hasta qué punto se siente cómodo utilizando tecnologías digitales en sus actividades agro ganaderas?
- 1 (no cómodo) 2 3 4 5 (muy cómodo)
36. ¿Qué le motivaría a ser uno de los primeros en probar una nueva tecnología de diagnóstico agro ganadera? (Elige solo una respuesta)
- Incentivos económicos Periodo de prueba gratuito Apoyo a la capacitación
 Testimonios de expertos Pruebas científicas
37. ¿Ha oído hablar de la tecnología de diagnóstico "Lab-on-a-Disc" (LoaD)?
- Sí No

Prioridades sanitarias del ganado y preocupación por las enfermedades

38. ¿Qué enfermedades del ganado causan más pérdidas económicas en su estancia?
(no es necesario rellenar todos los campos)

_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____

39. ¿Cuál es su mayor reto en la gestión de la salud del ganado?
(Elige solo una respuesta)

- Detección precoz de la enfermedad Costes del tratamiento
 Acceso de los veterinarios Cumplimiento de la normativa
 Mantenimiento de registros Otros (describa a continuación)

40. Pregunta anterior, si tienes otro reto descríbelo aquí

41. ¿Qué importancia tiene detectar las enfermedades antes de que aparezcan los síntomas clínicos?

- 1 (no importante) 2 3 4 5 (muy importante)

Contexto operativo e infraestructura

42. ¿A qué distancia se encuentra la clínica veterinaria más cercana de su estancia?

- Menos de 10 km 10–30 km 31–60 km Más de 60 km

43. ¿Acude habitualmente a esa clínica veterinaria?

- Sí No

44. ¿O tiene sus propios veterinarios?

- Sí No

45. ¿Dispone de conexión fiable a Internet en su granja/estancia?

Alta velocidad Básico Sólo móvil Poco fiable Sin Internet

46. ¿Con qué cantidad de personal capacitado cuenta que podría manejar los nuevos equipos de diagnóstico?

Ninguno 1-2 3-5 Más de 5

47. ¿Podría usted realizar de forma independiente todo el proceso de análisis, desde la toma de una muestra de sangre de una vaca hasta la evaluación del resultado con una aplicación en un teléfono móvil?

Sí No Según las condiciones

Terminación

Para cualquier pregunta o duda, por favor contacte a: Philipp Riedel, University of Cumbria, email: s2320803@uni.cumbria.ac.uk

Por favor, leé y confirmá escribiendo 'Sí' en el espacio:

Leí y entendí toda la información de arriba.

Tengo más de 18 años.

Entiendo que mi participación es voluntaria y que puedo dejar de participar cuando quiera.

Acepto que mis respuestas se usen de forma anónima para un trabajo de investigación.

Sé a quién contactar si tengo alguna pregunta o duda.

Al continuar a la siguiente página, aceptás participar en esta encuesta.
confirmá "Sí"

Aquí puedes ingresar un código con al menos 3 caracteres diferentes. Guarda este código; lo necesitarás si quieres/decides retirar tu participación de la encuesta más adelante

Su participación realmente marca la diferencia. ¡Gracias por formar parte de esta iniciativa!

B. Results

B.1. Results Yes/No/Depends on Conditions Results

Answers/ Ques- tion	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	107	110	142	138	132	134	141	125	83	98	20	95	77	111
Yes (%)	71	73	95	92	88	89	94	83	55	65	13	63	51	74
No	43	4	7	12	4	15	8	4	66	52	130	55	73	16
No (%)	29	3	5	8	3	10	5	3	44	35	87	37	49	11
Depends on con- ditions	-	36	-	-	13	-	-	20	-	-	-	-	-	23
Depends (%)	-	24	-	-	9	-	-	13	-	-	-	-	-	15
No An- swer	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.1.: Category: Full-dataset. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

Answers/ Ques- tion	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	23	31	46	42	38	39	44	41	18	23	6	26	18	28
Yes (%)	45	61	90	82	75	76	86	80	35	45	12	51	35	55
No	28	3	5	9	4	12	7	3	33	28	45	25	33	10
No (%)	55	6	10	18	8	24	14	6	65	55	88	49	65	20
Depends on con- ditions	-	17	-	-	9	-	-	7	-	-	-	-	-	13
Depends (%)	-	33	-	-	18	-	-	14	-	-	-	-	-	25
No An- swer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.2.: Category: Small-Farms. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

Answers/ Ques- tion	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	41	37	45	45	46	46	46	42	37	42	6	42	18	40
Yes (%)	85	77	94	94	96	96	96	88	77	88	12	88	38	83
No	7	0	2	3	0	1	1	0	10	6	42	6	30	4
No (%)	15	0	4	6	0	2	2	0	21	12	88	12	62	8
Depends on con- ditions	-	11	-	-	1	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	-	4
Depends (%)	-	23	-	-	2	-	-	10	-	-	-	-	-	8
No An- swer	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.3.: Category: Medium-Farms. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

Answers/ Ques- tion	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	42	40	48	48	45	46	48	40	28	32	7	27	38	40
Yes (%)	88	83	100	100	94	96	100	83	58	67	15	56	79	83
No	6	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	20	16	41	21	10	2
No (%)	12	2	0	0	0	4	0	2	42	33	85	44	21	4
Depends on con- ditions	-	7	-	-	3	-	-	7	-	-	-	-	-	6
Depends (%)	-	15	-	-	6	-	-	15	-	-	-	-	-	12
No An- swer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.4.: Category: Large-Farms. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

Answers/ Question	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	33	31	38	36	39	38	39	33	30	33	3	32	19	33
Yes (%)	85	79	97	92	100	97	100	85	77	85	8	82	49	85
No	6	0	1	3	0	1	0	0	9	6	36	7	20	2
No (%)	15	0	3	8	0	3	0	0	23	15	92	18	51	5
Depends on con- ditions	-	8	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	-	-	4
Depends (%)	-	21	-	-	-	-	-	15	-	-	-	-	-	10
No An- swer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.5.: Category: Dairy-Farms. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

Answers/ Question	B1	B2	C2	D4	E1	E2	E3	E5	F3	F4	H5	J1a	J1b	J4
Yes	65	65	87	85	79	80	85	77	47	54	14	60	43	65
Yes (%)	70	70	94	91	85	86	91	83	51	58	15	65	46	70
No	28	4	5	8	4	13	8	3	46	39	79	33	50	11
No (%)	30	4	5	9	4	14	9	3	49	42	85	35	54	12
Depends on con- ditions	-	24	-	-	10	-	-	13	-	-	-	-	-	17
Depends (%)	-	26	-	-	11	-	-	14	-	-	-	-	-	18
No An- swer	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
No An- swer (%)	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table B.6.: Category: Meat-Farms. Results of questions with No/Yes or depends on condition answers

B.2. Results of Questions with Scales 1 to 5

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	2	2	22	10	1	1
1 (%)	1.3%	1.3%	14.7%	6.7%	0.7%	0.7%
2	4	4	11	12	4	0
2 (%)	2.7%	2.7%	7.3%	8.0%	2.7%	0.0%
3	3	12	16	11	14	2
3 (%)	2.0%	8.0%	10.7%	7.3%	9.3%	1.3%
4	14	34	34	20	36	8
4 (%)	9.3%	22.7%	22.7%	13.3%	24.0%	5.3%
5	126	97	64	97	94	138
5 (%)	84.0%	64.7%	42.7%	64.7%	62.7%	92.0%
No Answer	1	1	3	0	1	1
No Answer (%)	0.7%	0.7%	2.0%	-	0.7%	0.7%
Average	4.73	4.48	3.73	4.21	4.46	4.89

Table B.7.: Category: Full-dataset. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	2	2	16	7	1	0
1 (%)	3.9%	3.9%	31.4%	13.7%	2.0%	0.0%
2	2	3	10	11	3	0
2 (%)	3.9%	5.9%	19.6%	21.6%	5.9%	0.0%
3	2	7	7	6	7	1
3 (%)	3.9%	13.7%	13.7%	11.8%	13.7%	2.0%
4	9	13	7	9	15	5
4 (%)	17.6%	25.5%	13.7%	17.6%	29.4%	9.8%
5	36	26	9	18	24	45
5 (%)	70.6%	51.0%	17.6%	35.3%	47.1%	88.2%
No Answer	0	0	2	0	1	0
No Answer (%)	-	-	3.9%	-	2.0%	-
Average	4.47	4.14	2.65	3.39	4.16	4.86

Table B.8.: Category: Small-Farms. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	0	0	4	2	0	0
1 (%)	0.0%	0.0%	8.3%	4.2%	0.0%	0.0%
2	0	1	0	0	0	0
2 (%)	0.0%	2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
3	0	2	6	1	1	0
3 (%)	0.0%	4.2%	12.5%	2.1%	2.1%	0.0%
4	3	11	13	5	9	2
4 (%)	6.2%	22.9%	27.1%	10.4%	18.8%	4.2%
5	44	33	25	40	38	45
5 (%)	91.7%	68.8%	52.1%	83.3%	79.2%	93.8%
No Answer	1	1	0	0	0	1
No Answer (%)	2.1%	2.1%	-	-	-	2.1%
Average	4.94	4.62	4.15	4.69	4.77	4.96

Table B.9.: Category: Medium-Farms. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	0	0	1	0	0	0
1 (%)	0.0%	0.0%	2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
2	1	0	1	0	0	0
2 (%)	2.1%	0.0%	2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
3	1	2	3	4	6	1
3 (%)	2.1%	4.2%	6.2%	8.3%	12.5%	2.1%
4	1	9	14	5	12	1
4 (%)	2.1%	18.8%	29.2%	10.4%	25.0%	2.1%
5	45	37	28	39	30	46
5 (%)	93.8%	77.1%	58.3%	81.2%	62.5%	95.8%
No Answer	0	0	1	0	0	0
No Answer (%)	-	-	2.1%	-	-	-
Average	4.88	4.73	4.43	4.73	4.5	4.94

Table B.10.: Category: Large-Farms. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	1	1	6	3	0	0
1 (%)	2.6%	2.6%	15.4%	7.7%	0.0%	0.0%
2	0	1	2	2	1	0
2 (%)	0.0%	2.6%	5.1%	5.1%	2.6%	0.0%
3	0	1	7	2	4	0
3 (%)	0.0%	2.6%	17.9%	5.1%	10.3%	0.0%
4	4	7	13	7	9	0
4 (%)	10.3%	17.9%	33.3%	17.9%	23.1%	0.0%
5	34	29	11	25	25	39
5 (%)	87.2%	74.4%	28.2%	64.1%	64.1%	100.0%
No Answer	0	0	0	0	0	0
No Answer (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Average	4.79	4.59	3.54	4.26	4.49	5.0

Table B.11.: Category: Dairy-Farms. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer

Answers/ Question	E4	F5	G1	G2	H3	I3
1	1	1	12	5	0	0
1 (%)	1.1%	1.1%	12.9%	5.4%	0.0%	0.0%
2	1	3	7	9	1	0
2 (%)	1.1%	3.2%	7.5%	9.7%	1.1%	0.0%
3	3	7	6	7	7	2
3 (%)	3.2%	7.5%	6.5%	7.5%	7.5%	2.2%
4	7	22	19	11	22	6
4 (%)	7.5%	23.7%	20.4%	11.8%	23.7%	6.5%
5	81	59	46	61	62	85
5 (%)	87.1%	63.4%	49.5%	65.6%	66.7%	91.4%
No Answer	0	1	3	0	1	0
No Answer (%)	-	1.1%	3.2%	-	1.1%	-
Average	4.78	4.47	3.89	4.23	4.58	4.89

Table B.12.: Category: Meat-Farms. Results of questions with scales 1 to 5 or no answer